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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

PONTIUS PILATE AND THE SHAPE OF THE WATERS¹

1. One Lake, two Lakes

In the middle of the Italian Apennines the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range raise amid cloudy mists. Ancient legends inhabit the elevated cliffs and the sheer valleys which mark this portion of the land of Italy: a Cave set on the top of Mount Sibyl is dedicated to the name of a sibilline oracle,

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for centuries the destination of adventurous journeys made by visitors who were coming from all regions of Europe; a few miles away, the Lake of Pilate, nested within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, awaited its own attendance of magicians and necromancers in search of a suitable place for the consecration of spellbooks. Legends we have fully addressed in the series of papers *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend* which provides detailed information on the whole legendary tradition, with the definition of a conjectural framework in which to set the origin of mythical tales that were not born there, as they were plausibly attracted to the Sibillini Mountain Range by far more antique legendary credences connected to the peculiar seismic behaviour of the territory.

In this paper we want to address a different aspect of the legendary heritage which is linked to the Lake of Pilate, one of the two specific geographical features in which the Sibillini Mountain Range's myth dwells.

We are going to address the issue of the shape of the Lake.

An issue, and a thorny one. Because the fascinating, sinister Lake we see today is not one Lake at all: it is two Lakes in total, and both small indeed. They are so small that, in times of climate change and global warming, they increasingly tend to disappear altogether during the hot, ardent summers that affect the elevated crests of the Sibillini Mountain Range with ever growing frequency: an effect which is worsened by the scarce amount of snow that happens to fall on the same cliffs during the once-frigid winters that mark a land which is now experiencing rising average temperatures all round the year.

So as a matter of fact today the Lakes are basically two, while once ordinarily there used to be just one, apart from summer droughts: in the past, the Lake of Pilate was seemingly bigger though possibly not exceedingly deep, as the literary sources appear to tell us. Centuries ago, the place was often indicated as 'Lake of Norcia', while today it is usually referred to as 'Lakes of Pilate'.

What has happened? And why? Was it a long-term process, possibly induced by climate change? Or, did any specific event happen at some point in time?

Let's start probing deep into this tricky matter. Because the answers are possibly more than one, with a central role to be played by the nineteenth century, a time during which major changes possibly occurred.

With the help of ancient sources and cartographies, and using new, previously-unpublished information, which we already presented in our paper *The nineteenth-century discovery of the Sibillini Mountain Range by the Italian Alpine Club*, we will be able to deal in deeper detail with this hitherto-unaddressed matter.

2. Portrait of a Lake, today

At the very centre of Italy the fastnesses of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines, stand out from the main chain as an impregnable fortress. On the southernmost side of this massive ridge, facing the crowned peak of Mount Sibyl, raises the titanic shape of Mount Vettore, with its huge, imposing mass, an arched behemoth that overwhelms the whole mountainous region with its elevated top and vertiginous, sinister cliffs.

Fig. 1 - Mount Vettore in the Sibillini Mountain Range

Deeply enclosed within the precipitous arms of this giant of stone, two small mirrors of pure, clear water lie in silence and stillness. They are the Lakes of Pilate, waiting in their solitary nest, surrounded by looming, overhanging versants of vertical rock.

Fig. 2 - The Lakes of Pilate

The Lakes of Pilate: two icy, crystal-like surfaces, set at the bottom of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, high up amid sheer walls of rock, quietly reflecting the sky above.

Whoever had the chance to climb the gigantic mountain and visit the place hidden between the cliffs of rock knows well the feeling of indistinct, dumbfounded awe that seizes a human soul when left alone before this overpowering might, echoing any step that may be taken, any sound and any word that might be uttered, with hesitant whispers, by the unwary visitor.

As we wrote in our previous paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, this is a truly blood-curdling place. A sort of theatrical scenery, ready for some kind of eerie performance. The very nature of the site is such as to convey the listed feelings, bringing to the mind a weird impression of apprehension and expectation. And this is the site where

obscure, sinister legends resolved to settle down: the resting place for a cursed corpse, that of a Roman prefect, Pontius Pilate; and the place where necromantic rituals have been performed for many centuries. A place which is marked by a legendary, otherworldly character (see our previous papers *Sibillini Mountain Range, the legend before the legends* and *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*) and is ruled, as we detailed in another paper (*Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend*), by the appalling power of earthquakes, owing to the peculiar seismic nature of the territory.

Fig. 3 - The waters of the Lakes of Pilate

In the present paper, we will not address the legendary tradition which lives at the Lakes of Pilate, a fascinating topic we already illuminated in full in the series of research articles *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend*, which includes the papers listed above. We will focus instead on the physical appearance of the Lakes of Pilate which, as we will show in the next chapters, once were known to be a single Lake, while today we are usually presented with two separate ponds, which come together only in

rare occasion and only partially, when melting snow and rainfalls provide the basin with enough water.

So what is the shape of the Lakes of Pilate today?

Let's start our investigation with the illustration of the lofty, impressive rocky cradle in which the Lakes are hosted.

3. Two, one, zero: the many faces of a Lake

What is the appearance of the Lakes of Pilate today? And, what might this appearance have been like in past centuries? To find the answer, let's start describing the rocky setting in which the present Lakes stand.

Mount Vettore is the result of the titanic strain produced by the clash of two tectonic plates, confronting each other over the full length of the Apennines and clashing with giant might in the area of today's Sibillini Mountain Range. Ten million years ago the mountainous landform began to raise its peaks and crests from the bottom of a vanished sea. The process lasted many million years and the geological outcome was the massive ridges we see today.

It was at the end of the Pleistocene, during the Würm glaciation, a period extending from 100,000 to 10,000 years ago, that the Ice Age produced the most impressive feature which marks Mount Vettore as we know it today: the glacial cirque, a colossal hemicycle carved in the very matrix of the landform, which gives the mount its fantastic, astounding U-shaped structure, a sort of immense horseshoe. A glacier made all this, eroding and grinding the mount's rock by its ceaseless motion under the pull of gravity, for hundreds and hundreds of centuries.

Today, the ancient glacier has vanished, but the savage effects of its incessant action are fully visible. Mount Vettore is hollowed out from the inside: a large valley (the Valley of the Lakes of Pilate) is carved in its bowels, going from the elevated cliffs above, the razor-sharp rim of a rocky semicircular wall, straight down to the lower lands below, surrounded by further peaks, including Mount Sibyl.

Fig. 4 - The glacial valley nested within the versants of Mount Vettore, with the Lakes of Pilate's glacial cirque on the top right

Up there, at the very centre of a vertiginous hemisphere of stone, whose walls are more than 1,500 feet high, the Lakes of Pilate stand, lying in their shallow cradle filled with rocky debris and feeding on rainfall and molten snow.

What is the size of this glacial nest concealed within the arms of stone of Mount Vettore?

In our previous paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate* we presented an image which easily shows the dimensions of the cradle in which the Lakes lie. A 'virtual' ruler is deposited in the middle of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque: it has a length of 1,300 feet and occupies the available space which goes from the steep southern sides of the mountain to the northern front edge of the glacial cirque, which then precipitously proceeds down into the Valley of the Lakes of Pilate. Thus, the Lakes live their solitary lives within this maximum linear dimension, with a width which cannot exceed that of the glacial cirque itself, not greater than 1,300 feet.

Fig. 5 - The glacial cirque of Mount Vettore with the 'virtual' ruler marking the available space

Within the above physical constraints, the Pilate's waters may present as one single Lake, two separate Lakes, or no Lake at all, depending on the quantity of rainfalls and melting snow.

An interesting article written by L. Martarelli et al. (*The Pilato Lake (Sibillini Mts., Central Italy): first results of a study on the supposed variations of its hydrogeological conditions induced by the seismic sequence 2016-2017, 2019*) effectively illustrates the direct relationship which is found between the present depth of the Lakes and the way they appear to visitors today.

In our present days, the bottom of the glacial cirque is not flat, as its elevation above sea level goes from 6365 feet at the bed to a central, raised elevation of 6430 feet: a 65-feet difference which accounts for the variable appearance of the pond or ponds depending on water levels.

Fig. 6 - The profile of the bottom of the glacial valley which houses the Lakes of Pilate (L. Martarelli et al., *The Pilato Lake (Sibillini Mts., Central Italy): first results of a study on the supposed variations of its hydrogeological conditions induced by the seismic sequence 2016-2017*, in *Acque sotterranee - Italian Journal of Groundwater*, Vol. 8, n. 4/158, 2019, p. 28)

Fig. 7 - The Lakes of Pilate partially connected by a narrow strip of water

Sometimes, when heavier snowfalls occur in winters, the two Lakes come partially together, so presenting themselves in the form of a single Lake as

in springtime the snow melts and fills up the basin to high water levels, surpassing the 6430-foot threshold. However, the overall appearance is never that of a single, oblong Lake: at its best, you still see two distinct Lakes, one reaching out towards the other by means of a narrow strip of water which establishes a link between the two.

On the other hand, during hot, dry summers the evaporation process brings the Lakes to complete disappearance, with the waters vanishing below the 6365-foot minimum level.

Fig. 8 - The Lakes dried up during an arid summer in 2017

The intermediate, usual appearance of the water basin is a spectacles-like, double Lake, made up by two small Lakes separated by a ridge of rocky debris, whose elevation is 6430 feet above sea level.

This is what we find today. Was it different in the past?

There are significant chances that the place may have undergone a certain degree of mutation.

To begin with, falling rocks and rubble precipitated by storms, landslides and earthquakes from the overhanging cliffs may have produced a raise in the elevation of the Lake's bottom: more rocks in the water, the shallower

its depth, and more chances to have it split in two separate ponds. Of course, within this framework the Lake would have been deeper in the past than we see today.

Fig. 9 - Mount Vettore's glacial valley encircled by lofty crests

And there is a second consideration we may put forward: today the glacial cirque's front edge, which overlooks the underlying Valley of the Lakes of Pilate to the north and sets the maximum potential height for the waters, reaches a maximum elevation of 6,463 feet; however, as we will see in later paragraphs, according to a nineteenth-century source it seems that the front edge may have collapsed some one hundred seventy years ago, freeing part of the Lake's water into the Valley underneath. Again, in this scenario the Lake's depth would have been greater in past centuries.

Finally, as a third observation we must note that the growing effects of an adverse climate change are hitting the Lakes of Pilate just as other areas in the globe: in recent years, snowfalls have experienced a significant reduction in the territory where the Sibillini Mountain Range lie, and the same applies to rainfalls. As a result, the Lakes are increasingly underfed, and their appearance is more often than ever before that of small pair of eyeglasses, or even that of a fully dried-up basin.

From these simple considerations, we have reasons to conjecture that the shallow, almost scanty Lakes we see today might have been much more significant in the past, with a Lake usually presenting itself as a single, deeper basin before the fascinated eyes of the incoming visitors, determined to perform necromantic rituals by its shore.

Is the above conjecture true?

Possibly, it is. And we are going to explore all the literary and cartographic clues which may help us in confirming, or discarding, our assumption.

4. When the Lake was one

As fully known to the readers of our series of research articles *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend*, the earliest mention ever retrieved about the eerie Lake which sits amid the mountains in the vicinity of Norcia is contained in a precious fourteenth-century manuscript, the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Pierre Bersuire), a French benedictine monk and abbot, who lived between 1290 and 1362. At that time, the Lake was known to be a single pool of water:

Fig. 10 - The excerpt on the Lake of Norcia taken from the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786, folium 301v)

«Amid the peaks which raise near that town [Norcia] there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them [...] walls were built around the shore of the lake, and watched over by guards, lest necromancers be allowed to access the place to consecrate their books to the demons».

[In the original Latin text: «Inter montes isti civitati proximos esse lacum ab antiquis daemonibus consecratum et ab ipsis sensibiliter inhabitatum [...] circa terminos lacus facti sunt muri qui a custodibus servantur, ne necromantici pro liberis suis consecrandis daemonibus illuc accedere permittantur»].

In that same century, a second reference is found in a work written by a poet from Tuscany, Fazio degli Uberti; in his *Dittamondo*, written in the second half of the fourteenth century, the Lake is equally referred to as one:

«I don't want to overlook the renown of the Mount of Pilate, where a lake is - which in summers is carefully guarded by watches on duty - because here Simon the Sorcerer ascends to consecrate his spellbook...».

Fig. 11 - The verses on the Lake of Pilate from a manuscript dating to 1447 of Fazio degli Uberti's *Dittamondo* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81, folia 1r and 95v)

[In the original Italian text: «la fama qui non vo' rimagna nuda - del monte di pillato, dov'è il lago - che si guarda l'estate a muda a muda - però che qua s'intende in Simon mago - per sagrar il suo libro in su monta...»].

But the most impressive, pictorial description of the Lake of Pilate is provided by Antoine de la Sale, who in 1420 ascended the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range and reported the details of his visit in his work *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*:

«First I will tell of the mountain of the lake of Queen Sibyl, which some name the mountain of the lake of Pilate [...] part of the Duchy of Spoletium and in the territory of the town of Norcia [...] This lake, in my opinion, is the size of your town of Moulins [...] In the middle there is a small islet made of one boulder which was once walled all around...».

[In the original French text: «Et premierement diray du mont du lac de la royne sibille, que aucuns appellent le mont du lac de pillate [...] parties de la Duchie despolit et ou terrouer de la cite de norse [...] Ce lac est en mon semblant du tour de vostre ville de moulins [...] Au milieu a une petite islete dun rochier qui jadis fut muree tout en tour...»].

Fig. 12 - The Lake of Pilate as portrayed in a miniature drawn from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5v)

The shape of the Lake, a single pool of water, is described by Antoine de la Sale as roughly circular. And we are given a full vision of this shape in the fine miniatures which enrich the de la Sale's manuscripted work, with the Lake standing in its rocky nest on the top of what we know today as Mount Vettore. Water seems to pour from the Lake itself, reaching down to the lower cliffs of the mountain.

A similar picture is provided by the French gentleman when describing the ghastly chariot that, according to the legend, carried the dead body of Pontius Pilate up to the Lake's icy waters.

Fig. 13 - Another portrait of the Lake of Pilate as contained in a miniature drawn from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 4r)

So, at the time of Antoine de la Sale, the Lake of Pilate was one, as further confirmed by the drawing contained in a later printed edition of *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, dating to 1527: in this picture, we also see the small island set in the middle of the Lake itself.

It is important to note that, according to Antoine de la Sale, the central islet is made by a single, large boulder («une petite islete dun rochier»): this remark seems to indicate that the Lake of Pilate, though presenting itself as a single basin at that time, was not particularly deep, as the top of a boulder laying in the water, huge as it may be, can emerge from the liquid surface only if the waters are shallow enough. And this conjecture is confirmed by a further remark provided by Antoine de la Sale himself:

«From the shore to the small island there is a narrow walkway submerged by the water which is five feet high as people told me...».

[In the original French text: «De la terre à celle isle a une petite chausse couverte deau a la haulteur de v piez comme les gens me dirent...»].

Fig. 14 - The appearance of the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *La Salade* (Paris, 1527), page between f23v and f24r

So at the beginning of the fifteenth century the Lake of Pilate was a single basin, though markedly shallow in some portions. In our previous paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, we also succeeded in estimating the size of the Lake as seen by Antoine de la Sale's eyes, basing on a specific remark written by the French gentleman («this lake, in my opinion, is the size of your town of Moulins»), in the original French text «ce lac est en mon semblant du tour de vostre ville de moulins»). The downtown area of Moulins-sur-Allier, the former capital of the Duchy of Bourbon, in central France, is around 1,300 feet wide, and it corresponds to the original castle. This is not so different from the size of the valley which houses the two lakes of Pilate which we see today, so that the rough estimate provided by Antoine de la Sale in his manuscript proves to be fairly right.

Fig. 15 - The French town of Moulins-sur-Allier in an eighteenth-century map and in a modern satellite view

A single Lake, nearly 1,300 feet wide, and remarkably shallow. Not a double one, made up by two smaller Lakes, the way it appears today. And the Lake's singleness is also retrieved in nearly all later literary sources which subsequently provide a reference to the magical waters that lie in the territory of Norcia. Only, we will later see that a few mentions portray a Lake in its summer condition: split in two distinct ponds, as an effect of canicular heat and scarcity of rainfalls during the warmer months of the year.

Despite its dual appearance in summers, which we will see later in the present research paper, throughout the subsequent centuries the Lake will be usually referred to and portrayed in maps as a single basin.

Pope Pius II Piccolomini, in his most famous letter, written on January, 15th 1444 to his cousin and friend Gregorio Lolli, wrote that «there is a place, in Umbria - which is known as the province of the Duchy - not far from the town of Norcia [...] he once mentioned to me the name of the lake and also provided a description of the place» [in the original Latin text: «locum esse in umbria, quae provincia ducatus dicitur, non longe ab Urbe Nursia [...] haec mihi vera esse asseveravit lacum nominavit et locum descripsit»].

In 1474 the Italian scholar Flavio Biondo published his *De Italia illustrata*, subsequently translated into Italian in 1542, in which he writes that «further above, in the territory of Norcia, there is that renowned lake where according to false rumours the waters would be replete of evil spirits rather than fish...» [in the original Italian text: «poco più su è quel lago famoso nel territorio di Norcia, dove dicono falsamente, che in vece di pesci, è pieno di demoni...»].

Bernardino da Bonavoglia, a Franciscan preacher who lived in the fifteenth century in Foligno, not far from the Sibillini Mountain Range, reports that «people say that near Norcia there is a mountain in which a lake named after Pilate stands...» (in the original Latin text: «dicitur autem quod iuxta Nursiam est quidam mons in quo est lacus qui dicitur Pilati...»). And in the same century Pietro Ranzano, a Dominican friar and bishop from Sicily, in his *Annales omnium temporum* wrote that «in the territory of Norcia there is a lake [...]: it is called the Lake of Norcia by the local inhabitants [...] a most elevated mountain was in the region of Norcia and a Lake was in it where demons dwelled».

Fig. 17 - Flavius Biondo's *De Italia illustrata*, the excerpt on the Apennine Sibyl from the 1542 Italian edition

At the end of the fifteenth century, the German knight Arnold von Harff provides the following account in his *Pilgrimage*: «After midday he [the lord of the place] rode with us up the mountain to where was a little lake. By this lake was a little chapel like a holy house...» [in the original German text: «Nae myttaghe reyt he mit vns oeuen off desen berch. Daer off stund eyn kleyne staynde see. By deser see stunt eyn kleyn cappelgen...»]. And in 1550 Leandro Alberti, a Dominican friar, wrote in his *Descrittione di tutta l'Italia* that «further high above in the Apennines, in the land of Norcia, there is the Lake [...] which is called the Lake of Norcia...» [in the original Italian text: «poscia alquanto più in su nell'Apennino nel territorio Nursino, evi il Lago [...] addimandato Lago di Norsa...»].

The many available literary sources we perused in this chapter seem to hint to a single Lake, with no duplication of basins as we observe in our present days. As we will see later in the present paper, duplication will be actually

observed, but only during summers, when the water supplies from rainfalls and accumulated snow fall short and evaporation caused by intense heat may severely deplete the basin.

Fig. 18 - Leandro Alberti's *Descrittione di tutta l'Italia*, original edition published in 1550, with the excerpt dedicated to the Lake of Pilate (p. 249)

What about ancient cartography? Can we spot the shape of the Lake of Pilate in the maps drawn by the greatest Italian and Flemish geographers of past centuries? Let's try to navigate the pages of the major atlases published during the sixteenth, seventeenth, eighteenth centuries and the first half of the nineteenth: we will always see our magical Lake depicted as a single basin (but with one notable exception, registered during a summer visit to Mount Vettore).

5. *The ancient likeness of a single Lake*

From the sixteenth century to the eighteenth we cannot retrieve any additional, largely-known reference to the Lake of Pilate in the European literature. And yet, the Sibyl's Cave and the waters dedicated to Pontius Pilate, set in the middle of the Italian Apennines, still seem to unfold enough appeal as to attract the attention of Italian and Flemish geographers, as manuscripted and printed collections of atlases begin to be edited throughout Europe.

And the Lake of Pilate, also known as the Lake of Norcia, is portrayed with its seemingly original shape: a single, magical Lake. A Lake that, almost certainly, was not the object of a direct observation carried out by the very

eyes of those same geographers: most plausibly its shape was reported to them by local correspondents and sources. Whatever the case, the maps we know bear no testimony to a duplicated nature of the Lake, though in hot summers the Lake itself certainly used to part into two smaller basins, as attested by two main sources we are going to address later in the present paper: a duplication which, apparently, will become more stable in later, more recent centuries, as we will see in the next paragraphs.

A most clear, most stunning pictorial representation of the Lake of Norcia, together with the Sibyl's Cave nearby, is presented in the renowned Gallery of Maps at the Vatican Museums in Rome. Designed by the Italian mathematician and geographer Ignazio Danti and painted on the walls of the Gallery between the years 1580 and 1581, the giant maps of the many parts and territories of sixteenth-century Italy shine with their blue and green hues before the astonished eyes of visitors.

Fig. 19 - A gorgeous vision of the Gallery of Maps, Vatican Museums, Rome

It is in the map which portrays the town and countryside of Spolegium, in central Italy, that we find the image of the Apennine area where the two magical geographical features lie: the «Grotta della Sibilla» opens its gloomy jaws not far from the towns of Norcia («Nursia») and Visso, in the middle of what we know today as the Sibillini Mountain Range; and the

«Lago di Norcia» stands as a deep-blue pool on high grounds near Mount Vettore, which is incorrectly depicted as a different mountain.

Fig. 20 - The frescoed panel which portrays Spolegium and the eastern portion of Umbria (Gallery of Maps, Vatican Museums, Rome)

Despite this inconsistency, which testifies to the fact that Ignazio Danti couldn't but draw most of his maps basing on second-hand information provided by other geographers and local correspondents, it is clear that our necromantic Lake was well known to sixteenth-century scholars. It was so renowned, just like the Sibyl's Cave, as to deserve a graphical mention in the geographical paintings housed in the Vatican. And it was known to be a single, sinister basin of water.

Fig. 21 - An enlarged detail of the map of the territory of Spolegium featuring the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Norcia (Gallery of Maps, Vatican Museums, Rome)

Only twenty years earlier, in the edition of the *Geographia Claudii Tolomaei Alexandrini*, as edited and expanded by the Italian mathematician Giuseppe Moleti in 1562, the Lake hidden within the Italian Apennines is shown as a single, irregularly-shaped pool of water, with the following accompanying text:

Fig. 22 - The map of the territory of the Marches of Ancona from Giuseppe Moleti's *Geographia Claudii Tolomaei Alexandrini* (Venice, 1562), table 19

«The town of Norcia, the lake and the Cave of Norcia are seen. Tales are told that in the Cave dwells a Sibyl, and Demons in the lake».

[In the original Latin text: «Nursiae civitas, lacus, et Caverna Nursiae, reperiuntur. In Caverna fertur habitare Sybillam, et in lacu Demones»].

quo plurima quotidie miracula mostrantur ubiq; nota. Nursiae ciuitas, lacus, & Caverna Nursiae, reperiuntur. In Caverna fertur habitare Sybillam, & in lacu, Demones. Fossembrona Forū Sempronii olim antiqva ciuitas, Recanat & Ricinetū

Fig. 23 - The Lake and Cave as portrayed in Giuseppe Moleti's *Geographia Claudii Tolomaei Alexandrini* (Venice, 1562), table 19 with the accompanying text

We find the Sibyl's Cave but not the Lake in the gorgeous editions of Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*, published between the end of the sixteenth century and the beginning of the seventeenth, possibly out of the fact that Ortelius' work was taken from a map of *La Marca d'Ancona* drawn by Vincenzo Luchino in 1564, which equally did not include the Lake of Pilate. However, we do find our necromantic waters in the work of a main competitor of Ortelius: the *Speculum Orbis Terrae*, in the edition published in 1593 by Gerard (or Petrus) de Jode and his son Cornelis: here the «Lake of Norcia» («Lago de Norcia») is drawn as an elongated geographical feature sitting not far from the Cave. But, again, it is a single Lake.

Fig. 24 - The Lake and Cave as they appear in Gerard and Cornelis de Jode's *Speculum Orbis Terrae* (Antwerp, 1593), a precious volume preserved at the *Biblioteca Angelica* in Rome

Fig. 25 - An enlarged detail from Gerard and Cornelis de Jode's *Speculum Orbis Terrae* (Antwerp, 1593)

The Lake and its companion, the Sibyl's Cave, are also staged in a most rare map contained in a manuscript preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library (Barb. Lat. 9906). The map was first set down by Mauro Giubileo in 1592 and then drawn by Giovanni Maggi in 1617: it shows a large basin

lying in the territory of Norcia, «hometown of St. Benedict and Quintus Sertorius».

Fig. 26 - The Lake of Pilat and Sibyl's Cave from Mauro Giubileo and Giovanni Maggi's map of the land of Sabina (manuscript Barb. Lat. 9906.3, *Vatican Apostolic Library*)

Fig. 27 - Gerardus Mercator's *Atlas sive Cosmographicae Meditationes de fabrica mundi et fabricati figura* (Duisburg, 1595)

We find a curious representation of the Lake of Norcia in the large *Atlas sive Cosmographicae Meditationes de fabrica mundi et fabricati figura*, published by the Flemish cosmographer Gerardus Mercator and his son in 1595. In it, the pool of water is shown positively connected to the hometown of St. Benedict via a streamlet or creek, a possible reference to the Torbidone river and its alleged, subterranean connection to the Lake of Pilate.

Fig. 28 - The Lake of Norcia as represented in Gerardus Mercator's *Atlas sive Cosmographicae Meditationes de fabrica mundi et fabricati figura* (Duisburg, 1595)

In 1620, Fabio Magini, the son of Giovanni Antonio Magini, the great Italian astronomer and cartographer, published *Italy - A General Description*, the last work completed by his father, who had passed away three years earlier. The book contained a bounty of detailed maps depicting seventeenth-century Italy, and Giovanni Antonio Magini did not miss the chance to outline the exact position of Mount Sibyl and the Lake of Norcia in two different maps: a first one which depicted the Duchy of Spoletium and a second dedicated to the Marches of Ancona.

Fig. 29 - Giovanni and Fabio Magini's *Italy - A General Description* (Bologna, 1620)

Fig. 30 - The Lake of Norcia as presented in the map of the region of Ancona from Giovanni and Fabio Magini's *Italy - A General Description* (Bologna, 1620)

In the first map, we see Norcia with its multitude of small castles lying in the vicinity: S. Pellegrino, Frascaro, Paganelli, Valcaldara, Notoria, S. Marco, Pescia, Castel S. Maria, Santa Maria della Neve, Ancaiano, Rocca Anolfi, Castelluccio, all featuring almost the same spelling as the names we use today. In the upper portion of the map, the Sibyl's Cave («Grotta della Sibilla») opens its gloomy jaws on a mount raising beside Mount Vettore («Vittore»). Nearby, the Lake of Norcia («Lago di Norcia») is drawn as a single, large water surface.

Fig. 31 - Another representation of the Lake and Cave of Norcia as found in Giovanni and Fabio Magini's *Italy - A General Description* (Bologna, 1620)

In the second map, the same magical places appear again, with the small hamlet of Castelluccio guarding the plain and the trails leading to the two sites: and the Lake is still portrayed as a single basin.

We can also observe our necromantic Lake in a work by German geographer Philipp Clüver, *Italia Antiqua*, dating to 1624: a nameless, ominous pool of dark waters sits on a mountain labelled as «Tetrica», the ancient Latin name for the most precipitous portion of the Sibillini Mountain Range, including Mount Vettore. So no doubt that this basin is to be identified with our Lake of Norcia, the town which lies close in the map.

Fig. 32 - The Lake of Norcia from Philipp Clüver's *Italia Antiqua* (1624), table between p. 640 and 641

At the middle of the seventeenth century it is the Dutch cartographer Joan Blaeu who draws the outlines of the Lake and Cave lying within the Italian Apennines in central Italy: with his impressive *Nova et accuratissima totius terrarum orbis tabula*, published in Amsterdam in 1659 (but other versions were edited by him since 1640), he shows the «Marca d'Ancona», once known as «Picenum», and the «Duchy of Spoletium», or «Umbria», in two adjacent maps, each featuring the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Norcia, once again with a single, elongated shape.

Fig. 33 - Joan Blaeu's *Nova et accuratissima totius terrarum orbis tabula* (Amsterdam, 1659)

Single, single and single again.

However, we know two remarkable, significant instances of literary and graphical mentions of a Lake split into two smaller lakes, out of summer droughts.

Fig. 34 - The Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave from Joan Blaeu's *Nova et accuratissima totius terrarum orbis tabula* (Amsterdam, 1659)

Fig. 35 - A different representation of the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave from Joan Blaeu's *Nova et accuratissima totius terrarum orbis tabula* (Amsterdam, 1659)

They date back to the sixteenth and seventeenth century. At that time, in the good season, the Lake could appear before the eyes of visitors in the form of two distinct Lakes, a shape that the water basin often happened to take during hot, dry summers, as it still occurs today with increasing frequency and throughout the year.

Let's begin from the oldest, graphical mention: it makes up a most astounding reference to the two famous, magical locations set within the Sibillini Mountain Range.

It is preserved at the Vatican. A manuscripted drawing. Of such a sort that it seems to plunge the reader straight into a gloomy journey carried out five hundred years ago. A journey into prohibited arts, effected not to a single, but a duplicated Lake of Norcia.

6. A sixteenth-century, first-hand visit to two Lakes

In 1982, a librarian at the Vatican Apostolic Library, Augusto Campana, was perusing the vellum leaves of a manuscripted volume preserved amid the tens of thousands of ancient, precious manuscripts which belong to the Holy See's collection in Rome. And he stumbled upon a stunning surprise.

The codex he was exploring was registered as Vat. Lat. 5241. On its first page it bore a date: 1566. And it contained a large number of references to classical Latin inscriptions, which some impassioned Renaissance collector had copied from monuments, marble slates, and graves dating back to ancient Rome. The volume had actually belonged to Aldus Manutius the Younger, a member of the renowned family of publishers and scholars from Venice, who were at the forefront of the revolution that, in the course of the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries, the new printing technologies were introducing across the European culture.

When Augusto Campana got to the folia 9v and 10r, he found something different from Latin inscriptions. Something utterly astonishing.

Fig. 36 - The binding of manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 (Vatican Apostolic Library)

It was a drawing. A drawing of towns and mountains and lakes. It was an ancient drawing of what we know today as the Sibillini Mountain Range. Untouched, totally forgotten, it had been sleeping for four hundred years, concealed amid the many pages of manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241, until a passionate librarian came upon it and brought it to light. And it was a very special drawing.

Because it portrayed a journey into legend.

An unknown sixteenth-century traveller, starting from the minutely-portrayed towns of Cascia and Norcia in the Valnerina Valley, had ascended the steep trails to the small hamlet of Castelluccio and had reached the Pian Grande, labelled in the diagram with the words «the plain of Castelluccio, two miles without a single stone» (in the original Italian text: «il piano del castelluccio son due miglia senza una pietra»). Then, the unnamed wayfarer had entered the secluded, magical kingdom of the Apennine Sibyl, beneath the shadows of lofty mountains which raised in that remote territory: «this mount is called the 'chiavetoie' (Vettore?)», he writes, «also known as The Mountain of the Sibyl» (in the original Italian text: «questa montagna dicono de chiavetoie, altramente La montagna della Sibilla»).

Fig. 37 - The drawing of the territory of today's Sibillini Mountain Range dating to the sixteenth century (manuscript Vat Lat 5241, Vatican Apostolic Library, folia 9v and 10r)

Fig. 38 - Cascia, Norcia, Castelluccio e il Pian Grande (manuscript Vat Lat 5241, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium10r)

But the very core of this sinister journey is drawn at the very centre of the diagram. It is called «the Lake Avernus of Norcia» (in the original Italian text: «il lago averno di Norcia»), a name which marks a significative narrative correspondance with the famous, classical entryway to the House of Hades set in Cumae.

It is the Lake of Norcia, also known as the Lake of Pilate. And, in this diagram, it is no single Lake: because there are two of them.

As we saw in the previous paragaraph of the present research article, in all the geographical maps available to us and dating to the sixteenth and seventeenth century, the Lake of Norcia is always and invariably represented as a single basin. However, someone was there around the middle of the sixteenth century. And what he saw was a Lake split into two smaller mirrors of water.

Fig. 39 - The Lake of Norcia (manuscript Vat Lat 5241, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 9v)

This peculiar, fascinating vision, contained in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and extensively investigated by Romano Cordella (*Il Lago Averno di Norcia' in un disegno cinquecentesco della Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana*, 2015), shows that at the mid of the sixteenth century the Lake of Norcia, at least at some moments of its life, was so shallow as to shrink to two distinct lakes, not different from the way we are used to behold it in our present days. Amid the two smaller basins, necromantic rituals were performed by visitors at circular walls made of piled-up stones, as shown in the diagram.

Two small Lakes, as opposed to the single basin always displayed in the known cartography that had been drawn throughout the same centuries.

What is the meaning of this drawing? And why the Lake appears to be split in two, while all other sources present it in the shape of a single pond?

What the unknown visitor's drawing seems to signify to the modern reader is that the Lake of Norcia, or Pilate's Lake, has never been particularly deep: it has always been a shallow basin, as clearly portrayed in the manuscript, with waters which go from a darker hue at the middle of the two pools to grey hatchings that represent shallower areas. And the scarce quantity of water detected by our sixteenth-century visitor is plausibly connected to the time of his visit, carried out in summer as assumed by Romano Cordella in his detailed analysis:

«The time of the journey is that of hay harvesting, in July or August, in accordance with the arid conditions of the lake as seen in the drawing».

[In the original Italian text: «l'epoca del viaggio coincide con la raccolta del fieno, cioè luglio-agosto, in accordo con lo stato siccitoso del lago come si vede nel disegno»].

So extended periods of drought during summers were able to deplete severely the water amount in the Lake, reducing it to two smaller Lakes: during the sixteenth century as today.

This is a confirmation of the remarkable shallowness of the Lake of Pilate, strongly affected by local weather conditions in terms of snow and rain quantities.

And summer will be invoked by another witness, Fortunato Ciucci, to explain the appearance of the Lake of Pilate a hundred years later, at the mid of the seventeenth century.

A duplicated Lake, in the form of spectacles.

7. A seventeenth-century description of two Lakes

Father Fortunato Ciucci was a monk at the benedictine abbey of Norcia. He was born in the same town. For four years, between 1648 and 1651, he was assigned to the small church of St. Scholastica, set not far from the town walls, in a quiet and isolated place amid the plain. There he spent his time in the elaboration of an historical essay, entitled *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia*: a true mine of information on the history, legends and traditions of the principal settlement of the Sibillini Mountain Range, written in a colourful, redundant seventeenth-century style. A prose which still bewitches the reader with the archaic, fanciful sound of long strings of words, depicting the vistas and notable spots which marked the mountainous territory. A very rare manuscript which is extant in four instances only and was transcribed and printed by Giampiero Ceccarelli and Caterina Comino in 2003.

As a lover of his homeland, Fortunato Ciucci cannot omit to include a comprehensive reference to the major legendary glories of the area: the

Sibyl's Cave and the Lakes of Pilate (and we must note here the plural). A full chapter, the last in the book, is dedicated to the two renowned, necromantic places lost amid the mountains of Norcia.

Fig. 40 - Scenes from the life of St. Benedict (sixteenth-century fresco, Church of St. Scholastica, Norcia)

His dissertation opens with a grandiloquent celebration of the titanic king of the whole land, Mount Vettore:

«No doubt at all, the sound of the Name of the great Mount Victor reverberates throughout Italy, together with the fame of the manifold, though ambiguous, Prophecies rendered at the Sibyl's Cave, and the Lakes that lie at its top; so I reckoned that I should dedicate an entire book to them, in which the inquisitive reader may satisfy his thirst for truth [...] Its Mount [of Castelluccio] is called Victor because it is the greatest of all, and it retains the same magnitude as for beauty and other remarkable features. [...] Like a gigantic Pyramid it so raises its peak towards the clouds above that only Jupiter's winged bird can reach its mountaintop».

[In the original Italian text: «Risuarda, non è dubbio alcuno, il Nome per tutta l'Italia del gran Monte Vittore, dei molti, benché incerti Vaticinj della Spelonca della Sibilla, e dei Laghi che nella sommità di esso giacciono, che perciò mi è parso convenevole farne un libro intero, nel quale potrà il curioso lettore appieno soddisfarsi della verità [...]. il suo Monte [di Castelluccio] si chiama Vittore per essere di tutti il maggiore, così egli l'istessa qualità ritiene in bellezza ed altre prerogative. [...] Questo a guisa di smisurata Piramide tant'oltre si innalza con la sua cima verso le nuvole, che solo l'alato augello di Giove vi poggia»].

Fig. 41 - Fortunato Ciucci's *Istorie dell'antica città di Norsia* (edited by Giampiero Ceccarelli and Caterina Comino, 2003)

With his sparking opening, Fortunato Ciucci immediately provides the reader a fundamental piece of information: the Lake is not a single Lake, at least in selected periods of the year.

Let's keep on reading from Ciucci's work:

«If on various Mountains many different waters can be seen; on this an astounded World cannot but ask how it happened that Nature could store Water, on the very top of so tall a peak, in two huge Lakes, as we will later tell».

[In the original Italian text: «Se in diversi Monti si vedono acque di varia qualità; in questo stupisce il Mondo come abbia possuto la Natura nella Sommità d'un Monte sì alto farvi ricetta d'Acqua in due grossi Laghi, siccome più oltre diremo»].

So the Lakes are two. Two basins, as we already found in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241, whose diagram was drawn by an unknown hand a century earlier. We will see that Ciucci is explicitly referring to a double configuration occurring during the summer season.

The extensive description set down by Father Fortunato Ciucci provides us with a detailed portrait of the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, with its arched cliffs and precipitous ravines, and a comprehensive vision of the two Lakes:

«On the elevated cliffs of Mount Vittore and the mountains of the province of Marche, which lies on the other side, and which make up a Liturgical Mitre; in the deep valley, at their very core where Winter has its perennial nest, locking the land in ceaseless elderliness with manacles made of crystal and chains of accumulated snow, there the renowned Lakes of the Demons are found, in the form of spectacles, with this very shape».

[In the original Italian text: «Sul l'alte cime de' Monti di Vittore e della Marca, che dirimpetto lì giace, quali formano appunto una Mitra Pastorale, nella profonda valle, in mezzo di loro dove ha perpetuo nido l'Inverno, che con ceppi di cristallo e catene di vecchie nevi tien serrata la terra in sempiterna vecchiezza giacciono i famosi Laghi de Demonj, in forma d'occhiale, in questa guisa appunto»].

Again, we see two Lakes. Again, their shape is that of eyeglasses, as it was a century earlier in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241.

Fig. 42 - The Lakes of Pilate nested within MountVettore's glacial cirque

Two small basins, further portrayed by Fortunato Ciucci in his accurate description. And the duplicated shape, writes Ciucci, is typically observed in summer:

«The first of them has a circumference of 1365 survey Feet, and the second 1137; and this is measured during the Summer season; however, in Winter and Spring, out of the water produced by the melting snow which flows down from the creeks that mark the nearby peaks, I saw from various signs that they come together making up a single lake; but in Summer, in the lack of running water, they split, so that they are seen in the shape of eyeglasses, encumbered by large Boulders of fallen Rocks, and their water is fresh and clear and their chillness is like frost, because on the left side perennial snow is found, which is known to be crystal-like».

[In the original Italian text: «Il Primo dei quali contiene Piedi geometri 1365 per circuito, ed il secondo 1137: e questo in tempo d'Estate, ma il

Verno e la Primavera per esser l'acqua di neve discesa dai Rivi dei vicini Monti, ho visto, e considerato da molti segni che si riduchino insieme e faccino un sol lago; ma l'Estate mancandoli il corso dell'acqua vengono a separarsi, come si vedono in forma d'occhiali, ingombrati da grossi Macigni di ruinate Pietre l'acqua dei quali sono dolci, e chiare e la freddezza è simile al ghiaccio, atteso che al sinistro lato vi sono continue nevi, dove è fama sia ridotta in alcune parti in cristallo»].

So at the middle of the seventeenth century a monk from Nursia, Father Fortunato Ciucci, saw the Lake of Pilate in the form of two smaller, separate Lakes: a typical summer condition, as he himself reports; a condition also attested by manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and commonly observed, as we will see later, in our present days. Not only during summer, but throughout the year instead.

Fig. 43 - The circumference of one of the two Lakes of Pilate as they appeared in 2016

What were the dimensions of the two ponds? Ciucci sets down the circumference of both Lakes. The ancient «survey foot», in the Papal States, was slightly less than a modern foot. Therefore, the circumference of the Lakes at the time when Ciucci wrote was nearly 1.340 and 1.120 feet: and this is actually the typical sizes we can register today for our two Lakes under conditions of significantly strong water depletion, when the two distinct basins present themselves in a fully-separated configuration.

The Lake of Pilate, in summer, used to turn into two different basins.

However, even though our ancient Lake happened to be so frequently reduced to two Lakes in past centuries, we do not find traces of such dual shape in old maps and cartographies: throughout the sixteenth, seventeenth and eighteenth centuries we cannot retrieve any image which portrays the Lake as two Lakes. Apart from Vat. Lat. 5241 and Ciucci's written report: two rare witnesses, with virtually no circulation across Italy and Europe.

This is a clue to the fact that the Lake of Pilate, in past centuries, was less prone to duplication. And its appearance was, more often, that of a single, sinister basin. Except in particularly hot summer seasons.

And there might be reasons for this. Reasons we will come upon when considering the state of the Lake in the nineteenth century and beyond.

However, before we go that far, let's continue our perusal of ancient cartography. What we will see is, as anticipated, the repeated portrait of a single Lake.

8. Eighteenth century: one Lake again (despite its summer shape)

When we begin to move across the eighteenth century, the representations of the Lake of Norcia appear to be consistent with the historical, widely-accepted tradition based on Antoine de la Sale's work, the early references by Pope Pius II Piccolomini, Flavio Biondo, Arnold von Harff and Leandro Alberti, the drawing on the walls of the Gallery of Maps at the Vatican Museums in Rome, and then the cartographic works published by Giuseppe Moleti, Gerard de Jode, Gerardus Mercator, Giovanni Antonio Magini, Joan Blaeu: single, single and single again. And this piece of information widely circulated across Europe, in printed books and maps.

In this framework, the sixteenth-century manuscripted diagram stored in the Vatican and the further manuscripted description written by Father Fortunato Ciucci in the seventeenth century, both providing a dual vision of the summer shape of the Lake, had no circulation and did not experience any quotation nor mention by anybody in Italy and Europe.

Between 1699 and 1703, the usual oblong shape of the Lake can be spotted in Silvestro Amanzio Moroncelli's map of *La Marca anconitana e fermana*, with an imposing Mount Vettore raising its precipitous cliffs over the Lake, which is presented as an elongated surface of water of considerable size.

Fig. 44 - The Lake of Norcia and the Sibyl's Cave from Silvestro Amanzio Moroncelli's map of *La Marca anconitana e fermana*

And another map, edited by Guillaume de L'Isle in 1711, portrays the Lake the way we already saw it in Philipp Clüver's geographical drawing: a single, dark basin nested within the rocky sides of the «Tetricus Mons».

Within the present research paper we cannot certainly overlook the capital work carried out by two great Jesuit cartographers, English-born Christopher Maire and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich from Dalmatia, who at the mid of the eighteenth century were entrusted by Pope Benedict XIV with the task to build the New Geographical Map of the Papal States, the

first Italian cartography drawn by the use of scientific measurements and ground surveys, with the aim to assess the actual length of the meridian arc which runs across the whole extent of the territories under the Pope's rule, cutting through the town of Rimini and crossing, at its very centre, the dome of St. Peter's in Rome. Unfortunately their comprehensive map, published in 1755, does not show the Lake of Pilate at all, as it only features the label «Sibyl's Mountains» («Montagne della Sibilla») in the area where the Sibillini Mountain Range raises its peaks.

Fig. 45 - The Lake of Norcia as it appears in Guillaume de L'Isle's map of *Regionum Italiae Mediarum Tabula Geographica* (1711)

This may appear as an inexplicable omission which is hard to account for. However, the whole occurrence is easily understood if we open the pages of the extensive, lively report written by Boscovich and Maire themselves about their own scientific expedition across the Papal States (*De litteraria expeditione per pontificiam ditionem ad dimetiendos duos meridiani gradus et corrigendam mappam geographicam*, 1755). The two cartographers explored central Italy throughout the years 1751 and 1752,

making geodetical measures and collecting the geographical information which was to be used in their map. And when they confronted with the «Sibyl's Mountains», in 1752, it was hard work:

Fig. 46 - The *Nuova Carta Geografica dello Stato Ecclesiastico* by Christopher Maire and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich, with the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range (1755)

«The tallest amid all the mountains which are found within the boundaries of the Papal States is the one that is known as Mount of the Sibyl».

[In the original Latin text: «Montium omnium, quotquot in ditone Pontificia continentur, editissimus est quem Montem Sibyllae nominant»].

Fig. 47 - The Sibillini Mountain Range as described in Christopher Maire's and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich's *De litteraria expeditione per pontificiam ditionem ad dimetiendos duos meridiani gradus et corrigendam mappam geographicam* (Rome, 1755), p. 161

It was at the beginning of October when, leaving the small town of Visso, on the northwestern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, Boscovich and Maire directed their course to the highlands beneath Mount Vettore and the remote hamlet of Castelluccio. The summer was already over and the weather conditions seemed to warn them not to defy the majesty of the high peaks above:

«While we crossed that valley [the Pian Perduto], the cliffs on the left side [the ridges to Mount Sibyl and Mount Vettore] were covered with dense clouds; up there, the snow was ceaselessly falling, and was even being transported by the blowing wind down to us across a remarkable distance, even though the sky over our heads was clear».

[In the original Latin text: «Dum autem iremus per eam vallem, jugum ipsum ad laevam densis nubibus e superiori parte contegebatur, unde nivem

etiam, quae perpetuo decidebat, venti ad nos obliquo ingenti tractu deferebant, caelo nobis sereno»].

tis editos , profecti sumus versus oppidum olim & frequens , & opulentum , Arquata dicitur , pagum exiguum transgressi , quem dicunt il Castelluccio . Dum autem iremus per eam vallem , jugum ipsum ad lævam densis nubibus e superiori parte contegebatur , unde nivem etiam , quæ perpetuo decidebāt , venti ad nos obliquo ingenti tractu deferebant , cælo nobis sereno . Porro in eo pago

Fig. 48 - Bad weather conditions in the area of Castelluccio di Norcia as described in Christopher Maire's and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich's *De litteraria expeditione per pontificiam ditionem ad dimetiendos duos meridiani gradus et corrigendam mappam geographicam* (Rome, 1755), p. 105-106

The two Jesuits arrived in Castelluccio, a sort of timeless, secluded settlement placed in the middle of nowhere, in which, they note in the French edition of their scientific account, «most people live through the winter season the way they use to do in Lapland [...] buried in their houses under the snow» («la plupart des habitans passent l'hyver à la maniere des Lapons [...] ensevelis dans leurs maisons sous la neige»).

It was not the case for any hazardous climb to Mount Vettore and the Lake of Pilate. So they just leave Castelluccio and take their way to Arquata, on the southernmost side of the Sibillini Mountain Range. However, this has never been an easy task, and the weather wasn't supporting them at all:

«At the far end of the valley which I mentioned, we fell into a most narrow gorge, which leads from the mountain of the Sibyl down to the Marches of Ancona; the narrowness of the ravine increased the strength of the wind, to the point that the clouds brought by the wind against the mountainside rolled and broke as sea waves do, and seemed to vanish into foam; our horses had great trouble in moving onward. We were told that this passage is often impracticable, and that more than once wayfarers had been lifted up by the ravaging wind with all their horses, cast away and crushed against the rocks».

[In the original French text: «Au bout de la vallée dont je viens de parler, nous tombâmes dans une gorge fort étroite, par laquelle on descend de la montagne de la Sibille dans la Marche d'Ancone: la petitesse du détroit

augmentoit la force du vent, au point que les nuages portés par le vent contre la flanc de la montagne, s'elevoient en se brisant comme des vagues, et sembloient jeter de l'écume, enforte que nos chevaux avoient beaucoup de peine à avancer. On nous apprit que ce passage est souvent impraticable, et qu'il este arrivé plus d'une fois que des voyageurs, enlevés avec leurs chevaux par un vent impetueux, ont été jettés fort loin, et écrasés contre les rochers»].

Fig. 49 - A vision of Arquata del Tronto from the steep trail leading from Mount Vettore down to the province of Marche, with the relevant excerpt from Christopher Maire's and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich's *Voyage astronomique et géographique dans l'État de l'Eglise* (Paris, 1770), p. 106

More than a century later, in 1876, the same perilous path will be hastily trodden by Count Girolamo Orsi and his fellow-colleagues of the Italian Alpine Club under a heavy rain, «taking the cragged ravine which heads to the Valley of the River Tronto: it is sheer and precipitous, scattered with rocks and with no plants at all, full of hardships and hazardous passages, through which we rolled rather than walked. It was a disastrous descent...» (in the original Italian text: «prendendo a scender l'erta dirupata che volge alla Valle del Tronto e pare quasi a picco, irta di roccie, nuda di vegetazione, piena di seni e d'asprezze, sulla quale più che scendere si rotolava. Fu disastrosa discesa...»).

So this is the reason for the absence of the Lake of Pilate in the fine, accurate map of the Papal States designed by Christopher Maire and

Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich at the mid of the eighteenth century: they never saw the Lake, and they completely overlooked the small mirror of water in the recollection of the unwelcoming weather and dire straits they had experienced during their visit to the Pian Grande and Mount Vettore, the «Sibyl's Mountains».

Fig. 50 - Count Girolamo Orsi's account of a descent from Mount Vettore to Arquata del Tronto (Supplemento al Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano, Vol. XI, no. 32, 1877, p. 541)

What happens if we proceed further in time to the first half of the nineteenth century? Again, we still find a single Lake, as we will see in the next chapter.

9. The Lake in the first half of the nineteenth century

If we proceed further into the centuries, in the second quarter of the nineteenth century we come upon the astounding cartography that was produced by the Imperial and Royal Military Geographical Institute of Austria (*Kaiserlich und königliche Militärische Geografische Institut*), within the framework of a comprehensive mapping project which was carried out across the territories subject to the rule of the Austrian Empire at that time.

The Austrian cartographers edited a series of geographical maps which also portrayed the areas of Italy that were included within the extended political reach of Austria, namely the Grand Duchy of Tuscany and the Papal States. This large map, made up by 53 detailed, accurate tables in total, was «built on astronomical and trigonometric measurements» (in the original Italian text: «costrutta sopra misure astronomico trigonometriche»), and was the product of a specific geodetical campaign which was carried out, between 1841 and 1843, by a geographer from Lombardy, Giovanni Marieni, who made the results of his measurement work available to the scientific community in 1846 with the publication of the volume *Trigonometriche Vermessungen im Kirchenstaate und in Toscana*. The Tuscany and Papal States maps were published a few years later, in 1851 in Wien.

Fig. 51 - *Carta topografica dello Stato Pontificio e del Granducato di Toscana costrutta sopra misure astronomico trigonometriche ed incisa sopra pietra a Vienne nell'Imperiale e Regio Istituto Geografico Militare*, 1851, the territory of Norcia and the Sibillini Mountain Range (*Österreichischen Staatsarchiv, Vienna*)

In this finely-drawn map, Giovanni Marieni carefully portrayed the area of Norcia, Castelluccio and the Monti Sibillini. Within the embracing arms of Mount Vettore («M.te Vittore»), with its eastern peak labelled as «M.te Pretara» and its western cliffs as «Balzo Borghese», we find a tiny, light-blue-colored mirror of clear waters: this is the «Lago di Pilato». And it is a single basin, though remarkably elongated, as Marieni correctly nested it in its oblong glacial valley. Perhaps a darker mark traced at the very middle of the Lake may possibly hint to a potential line of separation between two smaller Lakes; and yet there is no doubt that when the Lombard

cartographer visited the Sibillini Mountain Range and saw that magical Lake with his very (and professional) eyes, it was one.

Fig. 52 - Carta topografica dello Stato Pontificio e del Granducato di Toscana costrutta sopra misure astronomico trigonometriche ed incisa sopra pietra a Vienne nell'Imperiale e Regio Istituto Geografico Militare, 1851, the area of Mount Vettore (Österreichischen Staatsarchiv, Vienna)

Thus, from the fourteenth century onward, and up to the mid of the nineteenth century, we come upon descriptions and images of the Lake of Pilate which constantly portray a single basin, with two peculiar exceptions, represented by the drawing contained in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and the description provided by Father Fortunato Ciucci in his “Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia”.

However, this situation is rapidly going to change. Some specific event is possibly about to occur: an event that might have turned the usual appearance of the Lake of Norcia from one to two smaller Lakes, as its normal, most frequently encountered condition.

And the first published, widely-distributed mention of a duplicated aspect of the Lake of Pilate is to be found in an account written in the year 1876: a reliable narrative, written by an aristocratic member of the Italian Alpine Club.

Fig. 53 - *Carta topografica dello Stato Pontificio e del Granducato di Toscana costrutta sopra misure astronomico trigonometriche ed incisa sopra pietra a Vienne nell'Imperiale e Regio Istituto Geografico Militare, 1851, the Lake of Pilate (Österreichischen Staatsarchiv, Vienna)*

Let's read the words written by a distinguished, enthusiastic nobleman: Count Girolamo Orsi.

10. A Count, a businessman and two Lakes

In past centuries, the Lake of Pilate was usually presented by the ancient sources in the form of a single basin, with possible temporary duplication occurring during prolonged periods of scarce rainfalls in summer as presented in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and Father Fortunato Ciucci's *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia*.

But if the Lake was usually one Lake at least from the fourteenth to the mid of the nineteenth century, as shown in the Austrian cartography of the Papal States, while in our present days it is normally split in two even during winters, what happened to it? And when?

We have proceeded ahead in time for five centuries, up to the first half of the nineteenth, and we have found many mentions of the Lake. Now, we are going to see that something seems to have possibly occurred at a certain point in time. An event that possibly changed the nature of the place, from one single Lake to a basin ordinarily split in two separate ponds.

A first modern hint to a duplicated shape is found in an account included in a publication edited by the Italian Alpine Club in 1877. It narrates of a climb to Mount Vettore carried out by Count Girolamo Orsi and other distinguished members of the Club on 15 August 1876.

According to the original spirit which informed the then-young association of Italian alpinists, established in 1863 by Quintino Sella, a parliament member and minister of the Kingdom of Italy, their visit to the Sibillini Mountain Range was not a mere leisure trip:

«Our goal [...] is the investigation of the nature of the mountains; we intend to achieve a general progress, as we target, with our merry gatherings and personal enquiries, the advancement of science and trade».

[In the original Italian text: «Il fine [...] è lo studio della natura dei monti; è scopo la utilità comune, mirando noi nei lieti convegni o nelle indagini personali all'incremento della scienza e delle industrie»].

So Count Orsi's account, though pervaded by a number of romantic expressions and a sense of daring adventure, intends to provide reliable information and actual observations on many scientific aspects which mark the Sibillini's highlands set between the Italian provinces of Umbria and Marche.

It is within this narrative scenario that we find a first hint, in modern times, to a dual nature of the Lake of Pilate, as seen from the elevated, arched crests of Mount Vettore:

«The Valley of the river Aso, which first splits the mountain sideways and then longitudinally, divides Mount Vettore in two separate branches: we are currently on one of them, and the other is before us, where Mount Petrara stands, the most elevated peak of all (8123 feet). Between the two branches, at the very bottom of titanic ravines, the Lakes of Pilate are

found, fed by an extended volume of ice, the seed of a persistent glacier, which hides itself down there from direct sunlight».

[In the original Italian text: «La Valle dell'Aso, la quale dapprima lateralmente, poi longitudinalmente squarcia la montagna e divide il Vettore in due parti: quella su cui siamo, e l'altra là di fronte, ov'è Monte di Petrarà, il quale ogni altro in altitudine sovrasta (metri 2,476). Fra queste, in fondo agli enormi precipizi, sono i Laghi di Pilato, alimentati da quella estesa lente di ghiaccio, embrione di un ghiacciaio perenne, che laggiù si nasconde ai raggi del sole»].

Fig. 54 - The excerpt on the Lakes of Pilate written by Count Girolamo Orsi (*Supplemento al Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano*, Vol. XI, n. 32, 1877, p. 540)

Event though Count Orsi does not provide any reference to a duplicated Lake, he writes the noun «Lakes», with an intentional plural. And this is no casual usage, as he repeats the same word in a subsequent sentence:

«If the 'swallower' [the karst hollow lying on the Pian Grande near Castelluccio di Norcia - editor's note] had struck our minds out of the subterranean disappearance of waters, now [we are struck by] the Lakes of Pilate, and their deep-blue waters, and the frightful ravine nearby which goes down for around 1800 feet, where the river Aso originates».

[In the original Italian text: «Se l'inghiottitoio avevaci colpita la fantasia per lo inabissarsi delle acque, ora i Laghi di Pilato, e le loro acque sì intensamente azzurre, e l'orrido burrone che lì vicino sprofonda per un 500 a 600 metri, donde si origina l'Aso»].

Se l'inghiottitoto avevaci colpita la fantasia per lo inabisarsarsi delle acque, ora i *Laghi di Pilato*, e le loro acque sì intensamente azzurre, e l'orrido burrone che lì vicino sprofonda per un 500 a 600 metri, donde si origina l'*Aso*; e quelle nevi perpetue interposte ai tre culmini, là in quella gola nord-est del Petrarà, che danno alimento a quei laghi, non lasciarono d'interessarci a questa grande varietà di fenomeni naturali.

Fig. 55 - A further mention of the Lakes of Pilate as set down by Count Girolamo Orsi (*Supplemento al Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano*, Vol. XI, n. 32, 1877, p. 540)

Thus, Count Orsi and his fellow-alpinists did not see a single Lake of Pilate: they saw two. It was the summer of the year 1876. And this is the first reference we stumble upon, apart from Vat. Lat. 5241 dating to the sixteenth century and Father Fortunato Ciucci's work in the seventeenth century, which attests to the possible dual configuration of the Lake during the summer seasons.

However, Girolamo Orsi does not provide any specific detail on the actual shape he actually happened to behold, even though we can plausibly suppose that he saw what we are able to see even today: two smaller Lakes, divided by a narrow strip of rocky debris. A vista that recalls to the visitor's mind the typical shape of a pair of eyeglasses.

This is the very same description we find in a further account published in another issue of the Italian Alpine Club's *Bulletin* around ten years later. In 1887 Giovanni Battista Miliani, a successful businessman and owner of a large paper factory in Fabriano, not far from the Sibillini Mountain Range, wrote a narrative of his visit to Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl, which he had carried out a year earlier as a passionate alpinist and hiker.

On a clear morning of September, Miliani ascended Mount Vettore and ventured along the sharp line of arched crests that runs from the western side of the mountain to the east:

«From up there, I enjoyed the gorgeous vista which lies all around the giant of the Sibillini Range. Flooded in sunlight, I could see to the east the most beautiful province of Ascoli, while lost in the mists, very far at all appearances, I got glimpses of the mountains of Fabriano, and the ridges of Mount Catria; on the opposite side, amidst the clouds, outlined over the

cyan background of the sky, the rough cliffs of Mount Terminillo and Gran Sasso stood out in the distance».

[In the original Italian text: «Di lassù, potei godere la veduta magnifica che sottostà all'intorno di questo gigante dei Sibillini. Tutta illuminata dal sole, si spiegava ad est, la bellissima provincia d'Ascoli, mentre perduti fra la caligine, in apparenza assai lontani, si scorgevano i monti di Fabriano, ed il gruppo del Catria; dall'altra parte, fra le nubi, ma sul fondo turchino del cielo, risaltavano a distanza le aspre gioaie del Terminillo e del Gran Sasso»].

Fig. 56 - The account written by Giovanni Battista Miliani on his visit to the Sibillini Mountain Range (Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano, Vol. XX, n. 53, 1887, p. 272-281)

Among the many wonders, Miliani cannot omit a reference to our fascinating, necromantic waters:

«I passed a full hour in contemplation of the vast underlying scenario with the utmost enjoyment; then, by treading the wide hollowed half-circle which divides Mount Vettore from the cliff of Petrara, the most elevated

point, I headed that way. Beyond the Vettore's mountaintop, going across the crest, down in the valley on the left side, the Lake of Pilate is seen; in summer, as when I saw it, it has a shape of spectacles».

[In the original Italian text: «Rimasi circa un'ora a contemplare l'immenso panorama con grandissima soddisfazione, e poi percorrendo il gran semicerchio avvallato che separa la cima del Vettore da quella di Petrarà, che è il punto più elevato, mi diressi a quella volta. Oltrepassata di poco la cima del Vettore, percorrendo la cresta, in fondo a valle, a sinistra, si scorge il Lago di Pilato, che in estate, come quando lo vidi io, ha forma di occhiali»].

stanza le aspre gioaie del Terminillo e del Gran Sasso. Rimasi circa un'ora a contemplare l'immenso panorama con grandissima soddisfazione, e poi percorrendo il gran semicerchio avvallato che separa la cima del Vettore da quella di Petrarà, che è il punto più elevato, mi diressi a quella volta. Oltrepassata di poco la cima del Vettore, percorrendo la cresta, in fondo a valle, a sinistra, si scorge il Lago di

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Sui Monti Sibillini.

Pilato, che in estate, come quando lo vidi io, ha forma di occhiali. In tutta questa valle, nei luoghi più riparati dal sole, esistono depositi di neve, che assai di rado sgelano completamente in estate.

Fig. 57 - The shape of the Lakes of Pilate as beheld by Giovanni Battista Miliani (Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano, Vol. XX, n. 53, 1887, p. 281-282)

We are now fully in the fourth quarter of the nineteenth century, and once more the Lake appears to visitors the way it used to present itself in summer and is ordinarily seen throughout the year in our modern times: in the form of two separate ponds. And nineteenth-century alpinists, typically climbing Mount Vettore in August, begin to register this spectacles-like summer shape in their accounts.

Possibly this is still nothing different from what we already saw in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and Father Ciucci's account: an ordinary effect of typical summer droughts. However, we will see later in this research paper that this is the time in which a long-term depletion process is beginning to affect the Lake of Pilate, starting from the second half of the nineteenth

century: a dual shape for the basin will be increasingly observed as its normal, ordinary state.

Fig. 58 - The Lakes of Pilate in recent years

Nonetheless, there will still be occasions in which Mount Vettore's waters will present themselves in their former gorgeous shape: a large, deep, single Lake of Pilate. Not different from the basin portrayed by Antoine de la Sale in his fifteenth-century manuscript.

And this sort of vision will appear before the eyes of fascinated visitors as late as year 1879. Possibly for the last time in history.

11. Antoine de la Sale's Lake still in place in 1879

In our previous article *The nineteenth-century discovery of the Sibillini Mountain Range by the Italian Alpine Club*, we published for the first time ever in a modern research paper a stunning drawing of the Lake of Pilate dating to the year 1879.

In that year, Mount Vettore received a number of illustrious, aristocratic visitors: the participants in the distinguished annual meeting of the recently-born Italian Alpine Club, which was established sixteen years earlier in Turin by Quintino Sella and other eminent members of an affluent milieu that included politicians, noblemen, landowners and wealthy professionals, all enamoured of mountains and mountain sceneries, with their new appeal as a target for excursions in the wilderness and previously-unaddressed scientific investigations.

TELEGRAMMI PARTICOLARI
della Gazzetta Piemontese
Belle notizie.
Perugia, 25, ore 1.20. — L'inaugurazione del XII Congresso del Club Alpino riesci veramente imponente. La città è tutta imbandierata e festante. L'accoglienza fatta agli alpinisti fu cordialissima. Gli alpinisti convenuti sono 120. La presidenza fu assunta dal signor Balincci. In questo momento la sala è affollatissima; le signore sonvi in gran numero.

Fig. 59 - The opening of the XII Annual Meeting of the Italian Alpine Club in Perugia (Gazzetta piemontese, Year XIII, n. 235, 26 August 1879, p. 3)

The XII Annual Meeting was held in Perugia, not far from the Sibillini Mountain Range, in August 1879. The distinguished attendees, coming from all over Italy, were welcomed and entertained by the local fashionable set, made up by the rich families of noble ancestry which lived in the small Umbrian town, not accustomed to large social events, yet able to arrange

brilliant soirees at the gorgeous ballroom that was in Perugia. Amid day trips to the main natural attractions in the regions, a gala dinner and workshop sessions dedicated to the new role of mountains in the tourism and leisure sectors, the participants had the chance to visit the king of the central-Italian mountains: Mount Vettore, with its arched crests providing a breathtaking vision of both the Adriatic Sea to the east and, far away to the west, the Tyrrhenian.

The leader of the party was Giuseppe Bellucci, a professor and founder of the Umbrian branch of the Italian Alpine Club; he was accompanied by a selected group of forty passionate alpinists who bore blue-blooded family names and resounding professional titles. At the end of August 1879, they reached the gloomy, isolated hamlet of Castelluccio di Norcia, spent the night there, and then confronted with the great mountain which raised from the grassy expanse of the Pian Grande:

«The next day, after a nap on straw, they headed to Forca Viola, or Forchetta, and following a three-hour climb, they reached the top of the giant of the Sibillini Mountain Range (8.031 feet) and contemplated the astounding vista provided by charming peaks, their tops naked and the underlying valleys covered with green, gorgeous woods of hornbeams, maple trees and oaks».

[In the original Italian text: «L'indomani mattina dopo una dormitella sulla paglia, s'avviarono per la Forchetta, o Forca Viola, e dopo tre ore di salita poterono dalla cima del gigante dei monti Sibillini (m. 2448) ammirare lo spettacolo meraviglioso della bella catena, brulla alle vette, verdeggianti nelle valli per splendidi boschi di carpini, di aceri, di quercie»].

This short account is reported in the pages of a widely-distributed illustrated magazine, *L'Illustrazione Italiana*, in its first years at the time. In the issue published on 12 October 1879, a large space is actually devoted to the Annual Meeting held in Perugia.

But the most important piece of information presented by the renowned magazine is a full page dedicated to drawings which pictorially depict the event: a premium feature, the 'illustrations', that made that periodical publication so popular.

Amid the many images proposed to the magazine's readers, certainly the most impressive is the one labelled «Mount Vettore's top» («Cima del Vettore»).

And the mountaintop of Mount Vettore, represented under the threat of heavy, rainy clouds, is fully occupied by a large, deep, sinister Lake.

Fig. 60 - The crests of Mount Vettore and the Lake of Pilate in 1879 (*L'Illustrazione italiana*, Year VI, n. 41, 12 October 1879, p. 233)

This is, of course, the Lake of Pilate. An ominous, single, unduplicated Lake.

It seems to be no different from the Lake that Antoine de la Sale had the chance to see in the year 1420: a rounded basin, similar to the waters portrayed in the fifteenth-century manuscript of *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*. In both views, water seems to flow out of the Lake and into the underlying valley, a possible reference to the river Aso, which actually originates below the glacial cirque.

Thus, in 1879 the Lake of Pilate still retained its ominous fascination as a large Lake hidden within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, in central Italy. Just as it used to be represented in literary references and geographical maps, for centuries and centuries, apart from single instances

of duplication of its waters during the summer season (manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and essay written by Father Fortunato Ciucci).

Fig. 61 - Visions of the Lake of Pilate: the basin as portrayed by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5v) and the drawing published by *L'Illustrazione italiana* in 1879

However, something was about to change.

This is the last time we encounter the Lake of Pilate in its original, most thriving shape.

In the following years and decades, we will begin to meet further descriptions of our necromantic waters: descriptions of an increasingly depleted basin, ordinarily seen in the form of two separated Lakes. A change possibly to be ascribed to some sort of specific event, including potential earthquake effects, and/or a longer-term process linked to ever-decreasing levels of snowfalls and rainfalls. The first signs of a global climate change.

And the turning point in the above change may be conventionally set to the year 1897, when a new reliable visitor will register, once more, a duplicated shape for the Lake of Pilate.

Nothing new, one may say. As we saw earlier in this paper, summer duplication used to occur in previous centuries, too.

However, this time was different. Because snow was there, but this wasn't helping the Lake in maintaining its single appearance. Despite the presence of melting snow, it was split in two, like «a pair of spectacles»: the usual shape this water basin will present to visitors from them on and up to our

present days, with only rare appearances in the old form of a single pond, though similarly reduced and depleted.

Our next reliable witness is a most illustrious scholar: the Italian philologist, professor and future member of the Italian Senate Pio Rajna.

12. Pio Rajna and the first signs of persistent duplication

With the visit carried out to the Lake of Pilate by the renowned Italian philologist Pio Rajna, something seems to be changing with our necromantic basin set on Mount Vettore.

Because the Lake of Pilate appears to be gradually turning into a doubled mirror of waters, and not only in summers. Was it a gradual process, or, as it might seem from the scant sources available to us, did it happen in the course of a sudden, specific event?

Let's try and get through this truly tricky matter. With the help of the report written by a most distinguished witness: Pio Rajna, who visited the place in the last decade of the nineteenth century.

When Pio Rajna carried out his exploration of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in 1897, he was in search of the ancient legend of the Apennine Sibyl, in the wake of an increasing interest for her mysterious lore that was being aroused among scholars following the publication of insight papers by Alfred von Reumont and Arturo Graf, and out of the mounting philological quarrel over the origin of the German myth of Tannhäuser.

We fully described Rajna's visit in our previous articles *Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend* and *The nineteenth-century discovery of the Sibillini Mountain Range by the Italian Alpine Club*. Now we want to turn our attention to the most significant sentences he wrote about the shape of the Lake in his *In the territory of the Sibyl of Norcia (Nei paraggi della Sibilla di Norcia)*, an account of his visit to the Sibyl's Cave and the necromantic basin that was included in the volume *Studii dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (1912).

Fig. 62 - Pio Rajna's account of his journey to the Sibillini Mountain Range as reported in *Studii dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 233 and 244

The following excerpts are taken from Pio Rajna's account:

«The clouds, which had threateningly gathered around Mount Vettore, and thus at the Lake of Pilate as well, had turned their threat into action, delivering a storm on us».

[In the original Italian text: «Le nubi, che s'erano andate addensando minacciose dattorno al Vettore, e però anche al Lago di Pilato, avevano tramutato le minacce in fatti, regalandoci un temporale»].

In August 1897, Pio Rajna ascends to what he knows with the name of «Lake of Pilate», with still a single, undivided shape hidden in the singular form of the name. The illustrious philologist and alpinist treads «the trail to the lake» towards «the spot where the lake lies» (in the original Italian text: «la via al lago e il luogo dove il lago è posto»), until he gets to the impressive glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, where «a sheer wall of rock raises for nearly 1,200 feet, looming over the lake from its western side and looking like the pinnacled facade of a giant-scale church» (in the original

Italian text: «per ben trecentosessanta metri s'inalza la parete assolutamente verticale, che sovrasta al lago dalla parte di ponente, presentando l'aspetto della facciata policuspideale d'una chiesa gigantesca»).

And here is how the Lake of Pilate presented itself to the fascinated eyes of Pio Rajna on August, 15 1897:

«The Lake appeared to me divided in two elliptical mirrors, one of which elongates not in the middle but on one side instead, pointing to the other. The comparison with a pair of spectacles, which I heard earlier before from my guide in Castelluccio, is truly pictorial».

[In the original Italian text: «Il lago mi si è presentato diviso in due specchi ellittici, uno dei quali si protende appuntandosi, non nel mezzo, ma da un lato, verso l'altro. Il paragone con un par d'occhiali, che avevo udito dalla mia guida del Castelluccio, è realmente grafico»].

Il lago mi si è presentato diviso in due specchi ellittici, uno dei quali si protende appuntandosi, non nel mezzo, ma da un lato, verso l'altro. Il paragone con un par d'occhiali, che avevo udito dalla mia guida del Castelluccio, è realmente grafico. La lunghezza, da

Fig. 63 - Pio Rajna and the appearance of the Lake of Pilate in *Studii dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 244

Now the Lake is officialy recorded as a duplicated basin, made up by two smaller ponds. And as such it will appear in all later descriptions and photographic pictures.

Of course, there are occasions in which the Lakes still get back to their single configuration, as Pio Rajna himself notes when registering the dimensions of the water basin:

«The length, which I reckoned by counting my steps - very roughly, mainly owing to the hindrance opposed to a steady walk by the many stones - can be for each mirror some 500 feet. I reckon the front pond to be a little longer in size, if we do not consider the prolonged portion of the rear pond. However, as I told you there are times in which the two portions come together; and I guess that then, gaining some further extension at the two far ends, the overall length will not be much shorter than 1,300 feet».

[In the original Italian text: «La lunghezza da me misurata a passi - assai grossolanamente, per ragione soprattutto dell'impedimento che a un camminare regolato mettevano le pietre - si approssimerà per ciascuno specchio a 150 metri. Stimo un po' più lungo lo specchio anteriore, se del posteriore non si computa il prolungamento. Ma ci son tempi, come vi dissi, in cui le due parti si riuniscono; e penso che allora, guadagnandosi certo in estensione anche alle due estremità, non si resterà troppo al di sotto dei 400 metri»].

mia guida del Castelluccio, è realmente grafico. La lunghezza, da me misurata a passi — assai grossolanamente, per ragione soprattutto dell'impedimento che a un camminare regolato mettevano le pietre — si approssimerà per ciascuno specchio a 150 metri. Stimo un po' più lungo lo specchio anteriore, se del posteriore non si computa il prolungamento. Ma ci son tempi, come vi dissi, in cui le due parti si riuniscono; e penso che allora, guadagnandosi certo in estensione anche alle due estremità, non si resterà troppo al di sotto dei 400 metri. Con tutto ciò il lago non è più ora ciò che fu

Fig. 64 - Pio Rajna and an estimate of the Lake's size in *Studii dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 244

The estimate presented by Pio Rajna for the maximum size of the Lake of Pilate, 1,300 feet, fully matches with our own, which we presented at the beginning of the present research paper: this is actually the size of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, the physical space in which the Lake or Lakes are housed.

An important remark that the passionate philologist adds to his account is that the dual, spectacles-like shape of the Lake he sees in 1897 is not connected to the occurrence of any specific period of drought, as this same shape is detected during a normal, prolonged period in which the weather has ordinarily provided a customary quantity of rain and snow to feed the basin, possibly even in excess as Rajna records the presence of snow in August:

«I found snow in fair quantity around the lake; and normally Mount Vettore never denies this garniture to itself, as Antonio told me. In Foce (a small hamlet lying in the valley underneath) people told me that once there was a

period of nine years when a lack of snowfalls was registered in winters, too, but this occurred and ended twenty years ago».

[In the original Italian text: «Ho trovato neve in discreta quantità dattorno al lago: e per solito il Vettore non si priva mai, come dice Antonio, di questo ornamento. A Foce mi si è detto tuttavia esserci stato un periodo di nove anni, finito da un ventennio, in cui neve non s'ebbe neppure in inverno»].

Ho trovato neve in discreta quantità dattorno al lago: e per solito il Vettore non si priva mai, come dice Antonio, di questo ornamento. A Foce mi si è detto tuttavia esserci stato un periodo di nove anni, finito da un ventennio, in cui neve non s'ebbe neppure in inverno.

Fig. 65 - Summer snow at the Lake of Pilate in *Studii dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 244

So, when Pio Rajna makes his visit to the Lake, there is plenty of snow and the last drought dates back to twenty years earlier: but, despite all that, the Lake is split in two. And, he writes, «across most of its surface the water is thoroughly shallow» (in the original Italian text: «nella maggior parte dell'estensione l'acqua è bassissima»).

What's the matter, with the Lake of Pilate? Isn't there enough water in the glacial cirque to fill up the basin so as it becomes one? Or, has the Lake's bottom raised abruptly at its middle, so that water cannot distribute itself across the full length of the basin anymore?

How can it be? Why aren't rains and snows able to properly fill it up anymore, the way they have been using to do for centuries and centuries and even only twenty years earlier, in 1879, when the members of the Italian Alpine Club had the chance to behold a gorgeous Lake similar to that portrayed in Antoine de la Sale's fifteenth-century manuscript?

A possible answer seems to be suggested to our eager eyes just a few lines below. In that same account written by Pio Rajna.

13. A nineteenth-century catastrophic event?

Before the nineteenth century, the Lake of Pilate is a single basin, with summer appearances as a dual lake. Later, in the twentieth century and up to our present times, it is commonly reduced to two smaller Lakes. Throughout the whole year. Even when accumulated snow, as attested by Pio Rajna, may remain deposited as a white blanket within the rocky arms of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque at the mid of August.

Was Lake duplication a long-term, prolonged, continuous process? Or, did something happen there instead, that changed the ordinary shape of the Lake of Norcia, also known as the Lake of Pilate? What happened to that Lake, laying within the mountains which raise their cliffs in the vicinity of Norcia, Italy, at the mid of the nineteenth century?

Let's find out in Pio Rajna's words, which were written in the year 1897:

«All that considered, today the lake is not what it was in past times anymore. Around forty years ago, it broke the natural dike at its front, a barrier that never formed again. So Antoine de la Sale beheld a lake with a significantly different appearance, and deeper».

[In the original Italian text: «Con tutto ciò il lago non è più ora ciò che fu un tempo. Circa quarant'anni addietro esso ruppe le dighe naturali della sua fronte, le quali non si sono più riformate. Antoine de la Sale lo vide dunque notevolmente diverso d'aspetto e più profondo»].

Fig. 66 - The collapse of the front dike of the Lake of Pilate as reported by Pio Rajna in *Studi dedicati a Francesco Torraca nel XXXVI anniversario della sua laurea* (Napoli, 1912), p. 244

If the words written by the Italian philologist are true and reliable, we possibly find ourselves at a turning point in our research paper.

Prior to the occurrence of the breach mentioned by Pio Rajna, the Lake was larger and deeper: a single, wider Lake of Pilate, with transformations into two separate Lakes during summers only.

After the event, it split into two smaller Lakes. Basically throughout the year.

With his sentence, Pio Rajna provides our research with an astounding piece of information. However, how reliable is all that?

Fig. 67 - The northern front of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque today

According to Rajna, who is certainly mentioning what was reported to him by his local guides from Montemonaco, nearly forty years earlier the rocky front of the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore would have collapsed for some reason. And water would have poured partially out and down across the underlying valley. From then on, the glacial cirque, its front portion broken, was possibly unable to hold a large amount of water as it used to do in the past, whatever the rainfall and snowfall levels may be. Just like a cup with a broken rim.

Some forty years earlier, as Pio Raina specifies in 1897. Then, we are around the year 1860, or just a few years before.

Did anything happen in the vicinity of Norcia in 1860?

Yes, it did happen.

It was a mighty earthquake. An earthquake that unleashed its power on August, 22nd 1859. On this very land.

14. The earthquake of 22 August 1859

«The heat was intense and suffocating; the sky was encumbered with large clouds, murky and hideous, agitated and amassed horizontally towards the southwestern horizon [...] A powerful, vigorous bumping shake, accompanied by a deep grave roar, not different from the rumble of a great thunder [...] preceded six further wavering, horizontal shakes, which ended, as it seems, in the space of six or seven seconds».

Fig. 68 - The 1859 earthquake as reported by Abbot Leopoldo Mannocchi in his *Relazione del terremoto che desolò Norcia il giorno 22 agosto 1859* (Rome, 1860), p. 10 and 11

[In the original Italian text: «Il calore era stemperato e soffocante: il cielo presentavasi ingombro di nuvoloni bruttamente torbidi, scomposti, ed accampati in aria, segnatamente verso Sud-Ovest, in senso orizzontale. [...] Una validissima e veementissima scossa sussultoria accompagnata da cupo e profondo rombo simile al bombire di un gran tuono [...] precedé altre sei terribili scosse ondulatorie, or orizzontali, compiutesi, come pare, nello spazio di sei, o sette minuti secondi»].

This is an excerpt taken from the *Account about the earthquake that ruined the town of Norcia on 22 August 1859* (*Relazione del terremoto che desolò Norcia il giorno 22 agosto 1859*), written by Leopoldo Mannocchi. A frightful account of «the most horrible event that the world we inhabit offers to our sight»: earthquake, «a thoroughly frightful scourge, which many times has struck and ruined this town [Norcia]» (in the original Italian text: «il più terribile dei fenomeni che sottoponga a' nostri sguardi il pianeta da noi abitato, il paurosissimo flagello del tremuoto, che assai volte avea costernata e concussa questa città»).

Fig. 69 - A description of the 1859 earthquake by Father Angelo Secchi in his *Escursione scientifica fatta a Norcia ad occasione dei terremoti del 22 agosto 1859* (in *Atti dell'Accademia Pontificia de' Nuovi Lincei*, Vol. XIII, Year XIII, 1859-1860, Rome, 1860), p. 63 and 77

Father Angelo Secchi, the illustrious Jesuit astronomer and scientist who headed the observatory of the Pontifical Gregorian University at the Roman

College in Rome, and was sent to Norcia to investigate the effects of the earthquake, provided further details in his *Scientific journey carried out in Norcia on the occurrence of the earthquakes of 2 August 1859* (*Escursione scientifica fatta a Norcia ad occasione dei terremoti del 22 agosto 1859*):

«For a few days in Norcia people had been sensing many small shakings caused by earthquakes, yet owing to their limited significance and out of the customary occurrence of such events, the local residents did not pay any specific attention to that; suddenly, on August 22nd, between 1:15 and 1:30 P.M., with no previous warning in the air or anywhere else, a great blow was heard, as if a great artillery shot had been fired under the ground; as soon as this noise ceased, the ground itself began to be shaken frenzily, up and down initially and then horizontally, in three subsequent writhings, and with increasing violence for some 6 or 7 seconds».

Fig. 70 - Piazza St. Benedict in Norcia with its ruined building in 1859 as portrayed by Robert Turnbull Macpherson in his shot no. 187 (*Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione, Fondo Becchetti, Folder A, Rome*)

[In the original Italian text: «Erano già alcuni giorni dacchè si sentivano in Norcia varie leggieri scosse di terremoto, ma che per la loro poca importanza, e per l'abitudine contratta a tali scotimenti, non attiravano l'attenzione della popolazione; quando d'improvviso il giorno 22 Agosto fra le ore 1 1/4 e 1 1/2 circa pomeridiane, senza che apparisse nessun sensibile indizio nell'aria, o altrove, si sentì un gran colpo, come di una

fortissima cannonata sparata sotterra, e non appena finito questo rumore si scosse violentemente il terreno, prima sussultoriamente poi orizzontalmente, a tre riprese successive, e sempre con forza maggiore per una durata di circa 6 in 7 secondi»].

Fig. 71 - The district of Capolattera after the 1859 earthquake photographed by Robert Turnbull Macpherson in his shot no. 186 (*Centre Canadien d'Architecture, Montréal*)

The seismic waves unleashed destruction over the small town set at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range: «all this», writes Mannocchi, «was enough to plunge Norcia into utter desolation and slaughter of men» (in the original Italian text: «tutto questo fu bastevole a precipitare Norcia nella suprema desolazione e sterminio»). The building collapsed and one hundred people died beneath the wreckage. Only a small percentage of the six hundred houses which stood within the town walls survived: the vast majority of them disappeared amid the clouds of dust raised by the roofs and walls which were breaking apart.

The renowned Scottish photographer Robert Turnbull Macpherson, who lived in Rome for nearly forty years and was an acclaimed forerunner of the artistic applications of the new imaging techniques, had the chance to visit Norcia on 9 December 1859, only a few months after the earthquake. He documented the ruin of the wretched town in three superior, extended-exposure shots which provide an almost tangible vision of the effects of the seismic shakings on the land: the Piazza St. Benedict, the upper Capolaterra district and the small building known as 'Tempietto' are portrayed in all their desolated devastation, by using black-and-white contrast levels which are strikingly modern.

Fig. 72 - The 'Tempietto' in Norcia after the 1859 earthquake as photographed by Robert Turnbull Macpherson in his shot no. 185

Further shots, taken by a photographer from Perugia, Mariano Guardabassi, with an advanced stereographic method in 1863, a few years after the quake, set forth additional details of a barren Norcia: the ruined church of St. Francis, with its fine rose window; again Piazza St. Benedict with its damaged temple and portal; and the 'Tempietto' in its solitary, isolated position.

What happened there, not far from the Lake of Pilate, on that fateful day? And, did anything happen at the Lake?

Fig. 73 - Norcia after the 1859 earthquake photographed by Mariano Guardabassi

According to the contemporary sources, as written in Leopoldo Mannocchi's report, the epicentral point of the earthquake was located a few miles from the town, where a huge mountain raises:

«... the confidence that the tremblor was originated northeast of Norcia, that is from the foot of Mount Patino...»

[In the original Italian text: «...la certezza che il terremoto traesse origine al Nord-est di Norcia, vale a dire alle radici del monte Patino...»].

Faher Angelo Secchi confirmed this same observation:

«The occurrence we checked for sure is [...] that [...] all buildings are transversally damaged on the side opposite to mount Patino, so it can be considered as certain that from that direction came the main shock. This sort of damage seems to confirm that the speed of the disturbance was extremely intense, and that as the ground levels of the buildings were quickly pushed ahead and then drawn back again in a very short time, the motion had not enough time to propagate to the upper floors, resulting in collapse of the latter on their own front sides».

[In the original Italian text: «Il fatto però meglio avverato è [...] dall'esser [...] le case tutte lesionate obliquamente nella parte opposta a monte Pattino, onde resta certo che da quella parte provenne l'urto principale. Tal genere di lesione sembra provare che la velocità dell'urto fu grandissima, e che essendo state le basi delle case spinte rapidamente avanti e poi ritirate subitamente indietro, il moto non ebbe tempo di comunicarsi dall'imo al sommo, e la parte superiore venne così a cascare avanti»].

This position is no different from the epicentral point that will be registered more than one hundred fifty years later during the occurrence of another savage earthquake, on 30 October 2016: the seismic waves actually proceeded from that very same point, set at the foot of Mount Patino.

So, a powerful earthquake hit the region of Norcia on August, 22 1859. Modern studies, carried out by the Italian *Istituto Nazionale per la Geofisica e la Vulcanologia*, determined for that nineteenth-century tremblor an estimated magnitude of 5.7, on the basis of the effects described by Leopoldo Mannocchi, Angelo Secchi and others.

Fig. 74 - Seismic data of the 1859 earthquake in the territory of Norcia as taken from the *Istituto Nazionale per la Geofisica e la Vulcanologia's* database

Did the earthquake have any impact on the mountainous area where the Lake of Pilate lies, east of Norcia? Could this ruinous event be at the origin of a sudden mutation in the ordinary shape of our necromantic Lake, from a single, deeper basin to a shallower twin-pond configuration, as described by Italian philologist Pio Rajna in 1897?

Let's investigate further into this thorny issue.

15. A dramatic change in 1859?

When Pio Rajna visited the Lake of Pilate in 1897, he positively beheld waters «divided in two elliptical mirrors», which looked like «a pair of spectacles»: a different vista when compared with the customary representation of the Lake, from Antoine de la Sale onwards. A vista which was possibly usual and ordinary in summer, as attested by a sixteenth-century drawing found in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241, and subsequently confirmed by Father Fortunato Ciucci a century later.

However, when Pio Rajna sees the Lakes, a «fair quantity» of snow lies all around. Despite this most favourable presence, the mountain basin does not seem to be in good health: water is shallow and its shape is dual.

Fig. 75 - The Lakes of Pilate with snow in the good season, possibly a scenario similar to what Pio Rajna saw in 1897

Pio Rajna reports that, according to his local guides, «today the lake is not what it was in past times anymore. Around some forty years ago, it [the Lake] broke the natural dike at its front, a barrier that never formed again. So Antoine de la Sale beheld a lake with a significantly different appearance, and deeper».

Forty years earlier. Could that collapse have happened in the course of the earthquake that hit the region of Norcia in 1859?

In the original sources which narrate of the nineteenth-century seismic event, we can only retrieve partial information. Mannocchi does not provide any detail on the existing situation outside the town walls of Norcia following the shakings. Father Angelo Secchi reports that the small settlements north of Norcia (Abeto, Todiano, Ancarano, Capo del Colle) were extensively damaged. Large rocks tumbled down from the steep sides of Mount Patino, and cracks opened in the ground at specific locations of the town. Nonetheless, he states that Castelluccio di Norcia did not undergo any comparable level of destruction:

«Castelluccio, a small hamlet set 5 miles from Norcia and built on solid rock was shaken but not damaged».

[In the original Italian text: «Il Castelluccio piccolo paese distante 5 miglia da Norcia posto sul sasso vivo fu scosso, ma non danneggiato»].

sù deve imprimere maggior velocità ove trova minor massa : ora questa è certo minore nella vallata , ove manca tutto il carico delle montagne , che certo non sono cose di leggier momento a sollevare nè anche per le forze sotterraee benchè sieno enormi. Il Castelluccio piccolo paese distante 5 miglia da Norcia posto sul sasso vivo fu scosso, ma non danneggiato. Campi e le ville di Ancarano sono invece assai danneggiate e stanno in parte almeno sul terreno di alluvione.

Fig. 76 - A remark written by Father Angelo Secchi on the effects on the 1859 earthquake contained in his *Escursione scientifica fatta a Norcia ad occasione dei terremoti del 22 agosto 1859* (in *Atti dell'Accademia Pontificia de' Nuovi Lincei*, Vol. XIII, Year XIII, 1859-1860, Rome, 1860), p. 83

Fig. 77 - The area of Norcia as seen from the steep southern versant of Mount Patino

Certainly enough, the shaking, which according to Angelo Secchi was perceived as far as Camerino and Pesaro and even in Rome, also struck

with some might the most elevated peaks of the nearby Sibillini Mountain Range, including Mount Vettore and its glacial cirque, set only a few miles east of Norcia. But did this nineteenth-century tremblor actually affect the rocky nest which houses the waters of the Lake of Pilate?

We are given no specific answer to this important question, which would provide an amazing link to the remark written by Pio Rajna in his 1897 report.

What we know for certain is that, in that same area, in 2016 a much stronger earthquake, featuring the very same epicentral point set at the foot of Mount Patino, impacted visibly and titanically on Mount Vettore, the giant fault line running across its western side, and the most elevated crests that loom over the Lakes of Pilate, with the opening of giant fissures at many spots of the mountain, and the total destruction of Castelluccio di Norcia.

Fig. 78 - Effects of the 1979 earthquake described by Romano Cordella in his article *Visita ai centri del nursino colpiti dal terremoto* (in *Spoletium - Rivista di Arte Storia Cultura*, no. 25-26, Spolegium, 1981)

On the other hand, an earthquake of similar magnitude (5.8) which occurred in the same region on 19 September 1979 did not affect significantly the area of the Pian Grande, as reported by Romano Cordella in his article *Visita ai centri del nursino colpiti dal terremoto* (1981):

«... a few small hamlets, some of them substantially untouched by the earthquake (Castelluccio, S. Pellegrino)...».

Therefore, we are not permitted to conclude that the 1859 earthquake was the cause of any sudden change in the shape of the Lake of Pilate as a consequence of a breach in the natural dike set at its northern front, «a barrier that never formed again», as noted by Pio Rajna in his account. So we cannot confidently provide any strong confirmation of the piece of information written by the Italian philologist at the end of the nineteenth century.

Fig. 79 - The Lake of Pilate in 1879 (*L'Illustrazione italiana*, Year VI, n. 41, 12 October 1879, p. 233)

And the whole matter becomes even more entangled when we come to consider, once more, the drawing of our renowned waters as published in the pages of an Italian magazine, *L'Illustrazione Italiana*, in the year 1879, when the members of the Italian Alpine Club visited the place. As we already saw in a previous chapter, this source does not provide any confirmation to the scenario introduced by Pio Rajna with his mention of a possible collapse of the front portion of the Lake around the end of the 1850s: the Lake depicted in the magazine, twenty years after the 1859 earthquake, is just as hale and hearty as the basin portrayed by Antoine de

la Sale centuries earlier: without the least sign of a collapse of its front edge, and full to the brim of dark, ominous waters.

How can it that be?

Let's go and jump into this fascinating enigma, in an attempt to probe further into the possible meaning of all that.

16. Italian Alpine Club vs. Pio Rajna: who's in the right?

According to the words written by Pio Rajna in 1897, the Lake of Pilate lost permanently its former aspect as a single basin some forty years earlier, possibly in 1859 as a side effect of the earthquake that hit Norcia that year. In this framework, the alpinists coming from Perugia in the summer of 1879 would have beheld a doubled surface of water, in the form of «a pair of spectacles», as Pio Rajna effectively happened to describe it.

But they saw a single Lake instead.

And their testimony is fully confirmed by another witness, who wrote a different account of the same journey carried out to Mount Vettore in 1879. The witness is an aristocratic lady from Perugia, Countess Lucia Rossi Scotti, who was so bold as to join the distinguished party of men, and men only, that left the Umbrian town to make that daring expedition in the wilderness of the Sibillini Mountain Range. In a letter written a few months later, she recounted their ascent to the high cliffs of Mount Vettore and the gorgeous vista into the glacial cirque underneath they were able to enjoy from up there:

«... The greenish, gloomy Lake of Pilate, lying in that gorge out of the melting of snows...».

[In the original Italian text: «... L'oscuro verde Lago di Pilato formatosi fra quelle gole per il disgelamento dei ghiacci...»].

Again, no Lakes are mentioned; instead, we have one Lake.

Fig. 80 - The first page and an excerpt from page 9 of the letter written by Lucia Rossi Scotti on 13 november 1879 with an account of a journey to Mount Vettore (Biblioteca Comunale Augusta, Perugia)

Is something wrong with our tentative reconstruction of the possible event which led to a change in the shape of the Lake? And, did any such event really happen?

If Pio Rajna was right, how could the members of the Italian Alpine Club see a Lake of Pilato in a shape that was typical of older days? How could they observe a single basin, an aspect which sure enough nobody ever had the chance to behold again in more recent years, as we will see in later paragraphs?

There is no positive, confident answer to these questions.

If we stick to the proof provided by our 1879 magazine, *L'Illustrazione Italiana*, and the words written by Countess Rossi Scotti, in the final quarter of the nineteenth century the Lake still happened to appear the way it was four hundred sixty years earlier, when Antoine de la Sale paid his visit to the land of the Sibyl.

For the sake of completeness, let's ask ourselves a further, ultimate question: is there any chance of a possible mistake having been made by the editors of *L'Illustrazione Italiana*?

We might try to consider that the magazine, which enjoyed a favorable renown owing to the high-quality drawings it used to publish, was overwhelmed at the time by the many sketches and descriptions that had been flowing in, sent by the enthusiastic attendees of the Annual Meeting: «From the Alpinist congress held in Perugia drawings and accounts were shipped to the *Illustrazione Italiana*; we publish the drawings of the trips to Mount Vettore and the Gran Sasso of Italy; the space is not enough to publish the most charming descriptions, written by the Alpinists, which complemented the sketches...».

[In the original Italian text: «Dal congresso degli Alpinisti tenuto a Perugia sono giunti all'illustrazione disegni e descrizioni; pubblichiamo i disegni dell'escursione al Monte Vettore e al Gran Sasso d'Italia; lo spazio ci manca per pubblicare le bellissime descrizioni colle quali accompagnavano i disegni gli egregi alpinisti...»].

Maybe the editorial staff of the *L'Illustrazione* picked the sinister drawing which depicted the Lake of Pilate as it was in the past, while a second, unpublished sketch, less emotional, showed the Lakes in their true, duplicated form, as they possibly appeared to the alpinists. So the readers were given a vision of the Lake as it was earlier, and not as it was during the actual 1879 visit. And, perhaps, Lucia Rossi Scotti, who was no scientist nor scholar, did just write the sentence «... the greenish, gloomy Lake of Pilate...» even though he actually saw two ponds: an inaccuracy which would be fully pardonable with a Countess.

GLI ALPINISTI AL MONTE VETTORE E AL GRAN SASSO D'ITALIA.

L'Alpinismo fa progressi in Italia, si estende lungo tutte le falde delle Alpi, in Italia l'Appennino, lo segue sino all'estrema punta dello stivale, passa lo stretto e si dirama nella Trinacria. Da tutti i centri che si formano spiccansi arditi gli alpinisti a ricercare le più alte vette; i meno arditi si contentano delle cime più modeste e poco a poco gli acrocori, i sollevamenti, i gioghi sono percorsi, studiati, descritti; ad ogni passo si scoprono meraviglie, l'entusiasmo per le deliziose gite si propaga, e l'Alpinismo man mano entra nei costumi, stringe affezioni, amicizie, rapporti, fonda società, le collega e favorisce lo studio della geologia e della orografia nazionale.

Dal congresso degli Alpinisti tenuto a Perugia sono giunti all'ILLUSTRAZIONE disegni e descrizioni; pubblichiamo i disegni dell'escursione al Monte Vettore e al Gran Sasso d'Italia; lo spazio ci manca per pubblicare le bellissime descrizioni colle quali accompagnavano i disegni gli egregi alpinisti ingegneri E. Martinori e sig. R. Avanzi. Riassumeremo però la loro narrazione.

Fig. 81 - An excerpt from the article on the journey of the Italian alpinists to Mount Vettore in 1879 (L'illustrazione italiana, Anno VI, n. 41, 12 ottobre 1879, p. 1 and 231)

However, too many conjectures are involved in our attempt to stick to our assumption of a dual Lake in 1879, as a result of a potential, unproven collapse of the front edge of the Lake of Pilate in 1859. And so our whole effort seems to reduce to a mere, useless exercise.

Therefore, at this stage of our research, we can only accept the fact that in the year 1879 the Lake of Pilate had still the ability to appear to visitors in the form of a large, rounded, single basin, as portrayed in the pages of *L'illustrazione italiana*. Even though this piece of information appears to be in full contrast with the words written by Pio Rajna in 1897, which are possibly based on unreliable, erroneous words told to him by his local guides.

Further investigation will be needed to shed additional light on this puzzling issue, with specific research to be carried out at the historical archive in Montemonaco, the small town sitting on a hill before the cliff of Mount Sibyl, in search of hints and references to a possible depletion of the Lake which might have occurred at the mid of the nineteenth century, with a potential discharge of water down into the underlying valley and the course of the river Aso.

And there is also a further potential occurrence which might have dramatically altered the shape of the Lake of Pilate in this very same period. But we will confront with this possibility in a later chapter.

At the moment, only one thing seems to be certain: after 1879, nobody had the chance to see the Lake of Pilate in its impressive, single semblance ever again. From the end of the nineteenth century on, its ordinary shape will always be dual, with rare returns to an elongated, single-basin configuration in case of abundance of rainfalls and snowfalls.

We are now entering the final, twentieth-century phase of the life of our necromantic Lake. Let's see what happens.

17. The twentieth century's Lakes

The Lakes of Pilate. Two fully separate Lakes, or, when at their best, two ponds connected by a slim stretch of water.

This is the shape that, from the end of the nineteenth century, throughout the twentieth and beyond, we finally observe for the basin set within the arms of Mount Vettore.

There will be no large, extended, single Lake anymore. Starting from the words written by Pio Rajna in 1897, which reverberate the same words already set down by Girolamo Orsi and Giovanni Battista Miliani a few years before, we will always encounter representations and descriptions of a substantially duplicated pond, with moments of extreme depletion and even total dryness.

A first image of a Lake of Pilate which is gradually splitting in two isolated mirrors of water is presented in the framework of a large mapping project which was initiated by the Kingdom of Italy in the year 1872 for the cartographic coverage of the whole Italian peninsula.

Between the end of the nineteenth century and the first half of the twentieth, the Italian Military Geographical Institute began to release a comprehensive cartography of the Italian territory, with a 1:100.000 scale. The complete series will include 285 sheets, each divided into four quadrants at a higher scale of 1:50.000.

The earliest phase of development of the above collection of sheets and quadrants is indicated as «first measurement campaign» («prima levata» in Italian). To this initial stage belongs the second quadrant of Sheet 132, drawn in 1895: it is the map of the territory of Arquata del Tronto, on the southern side of Mount Vettore. And, in it, we are given a vision of the Lake of Pilate as it appeared to visitors only two years before the place was reached by Pio Rajna.

Fig. 82 - The Lake of Pilate in the cartography drawn by the Italian Geographical Military Institute at the end of the nineteenth century (Istituto Geografico Militare, Carta d'Italia, foglio 132, quadrante II, *Arquata del Tronto*, scale 1:50.000, 1895)

Mineralogy and Geology of the Department of Agronomy at the University of Perugia, who drafted a first comprehensive catalogue of the Umbrian hollows, including the Sibyl's Cave on Mount Sibyl, of which he drew a most famous map, dating to 1946 and depicting the entrance chamber.

In his *Circulation of subterranean waters in the plateau of Castelluccio* (1947), he provides a chart of the Pian Grande and Mount Vettore, which was set down following a number of on-site, geological-oriented surveys. And the shape of the Lake he portrays is very similar to that shown in the map released in 1895 by the Military Geographical Institute: the waters are marked by a deep notch at the middle of the basin, a clear sign of a tendency to part in two separate ponds.

Fig. 84 - The Lake of Pilate in a diagram sketched by Cesare Lippi-Boncambi in 1947 (Cesare Lippi-Boncambi, *Idrologia sotterranea dell'Altipiano di Castelluccio*, in *Annali dell'Istituto di Mineralogia e Geologia dell'Università degli Studi di Perugia*, Perugia, 1947, p. 104-118)

In a 1952 map of the territory of Arquata del Tronto, edited by the Italian Geographical Military Institute, we see a hale and hearty Lake of Pilate: its shape is exceedingly elongated, but the dividing notch is almost vanished, and the two basins appear to be fully connected via an adequate quantity of water. However, this was not the actual truth about the real conditions of the Lake set within the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 85 - The Lake of Pilate in a map published by the Italian Geographical Military Institute in 1952 (Istituto Geografico Militare, Carta d'Italia, foglio 132, quadrante II, *Arquata del Tronto*, scale 1:25.000, 1952)

In that same year, a photographic postcard sent from the small town of Montemonaco to Rome portrays the Lake as it really was around that same period of time: a depleted basin, its waters almost completely parted by a rocky tongue covered with snow. The ancient, single, rounded pond depicted by Antoine de la Sale was definitely gone; and no hint to the likeness of the impressive Lake represented in the magazine *L'Illustrazione Italiana* in 1879 can be retrieved anymore.

Fig. 86 - A postcard with an image of the Lake of Pilate sent from Montemonaco to Rome in 1952

From now on, the decline in the water level observed at the Lake of Pilate appears to be inexorable.

In 1954 an aircraft of the Military Geographical Institute, flying at an altitude of 19,600 feet, shot an aerial photograph of the land down below. The black-and-white, high-resolution image shows a pair of distinct Lakes, a rocky stretch fully protruding between the two mirrors of water.

And possibly to 1956 is to be dated another postcard which shows the sad reality of a once-single Lake: the two mirrors of waters are now portrayed in their isolation, with arms filled with shallow water that seem to make an attempt to reach one another. But it is just a tentative endeavour: it is clear that something has changed forever, and the two small Lakes never again will return to be a single, ominous Lake.

Again, in another photographic postcard sent in 1960 and possibly shot in the late 1950s we find a Lake of Pilate only poorly filled with water, the

southern pond stretching out its finger to reunite with its fellow-basin to the north.

Fig. 87 - An aerial photograph taken by an aircraft of the Istituto Geografico Militare showing Castelluccio di Norcia, the Pian Grande, Mount Vettore and the Lakes of Pilate (Istituto Geografico Militare, sheet 132, strip 44, shot 1434, scale 1:30.000, altitude 6.000 meters, taken on 1 september 1954 with an airborne Fairchild camera)

Fig. 88 - A postcard dating to the middle of the 1950s featuring the Lakes of Pilate

Fig. 89 - A postcard with a vision of the Lakes of Pilate shot in the late 1950s

Fig. 90 - An aerial photograph taken by an aircraft of the Istituto Geografico Militare showing the Sibillini Mountain Range and the Lakes of Pilate (Istituto Geografico Militare, sheet 132, strip 13, shot 96, scale 1:36.000, altitude 7.220 meters, taken on 4 october 1991)

Thus a dual shape of the Lakes of Pilate will be the ordinary condition normally encountered throughout the twentieth century, as thousands of hikers who have repeatedly been visiting the Sibillini Mountain Range in the final quarter of the last century know well, and as attested by another aerial photograph, this time shot in the early fall of 1991.

So, the healthy Lake overflowing with water and popping up merrily from a later map published by the Military Geographical Institute in 2008 seems to be a mere ghost of some earlier site survey effected by the Italian geographers long time before: in that years, the Lake's real conditions were significantly sadder, and water's depletion was getting worse and worse.

Because now we have finally reached our twenty-first century.

And here are our Lakes of Pilate of today. In the next chapter.

Fig. 91 - The Lake of Pilate in a map published by the Italian Military Geographical Institute in 2008 (Istituto Geografico Militare, Carta Topografica d'Italia, foglio 325, *Visso*, scale 1:50.000, 2008)

18. The Lakes, today

You may park your car at Forca di Presta, the pass set between Umbria and Marche, on the southern edge of Mount Vettore: from there, you may climb the titanic mountain up to the shelter 'Rifugio Zilioli'; then the trail leads straight down into the glacial cirque. Or, as an alternative track, you may reach the isolated hamlet of Foce di Montemonaco, and then walk up the valley of River Aso and get to the glacial cirque from below.

In both cases, you will get to the astounding setting in which the Lakes of Pilate lie: two enchanted, fascinating mirrors of greenish-blue waters surmounted by lofty towers of sheer rock.

And the vista is even more overwhelming from high above, if you are so bold as to walk the narrow, arched crests of Mount Vettore, set between precipitous ravines on both sides: the Lakes, down below, appear to be lost in their glacial cradle, with all their load of legends and sinister tales.

Fig. 92 - The Lakes of Pilate as seen from within Mount Vettore's glacial cirque

Fig. 93 - Walking the crests of Mount Vettore

However, when you happen to behold this place hidden within the most secret heart of Mount Vettore, in the very core of the Sibillini Mountain Range, an undisputable fact is to be noted: the Lakes are always two.

In our present days, nobody has ever had the chance to see a large single Lake anymore, the way it was depicted by Antoine de la Sale in his fifteenth-century manuscript or, in more recent times, by the magazine *L'Illustrazione Italiana* in 1879.

The large, rounded, or even elongated Lake of Pilate, as portrayed in numerous maps and described by many ancient literary sources, is lost forever.

Fig. 94 - The Lakes of Pilate at their best in June 2010

Today, in years when rainfalls and snowfalls are copious and summers are not exceedingly hot, visitors may still hope to see the Lakes partially joined to form a sort of oblong, indented basin: this condition is documented by a number of pictures taken in the first fifteen years of the twenty-first century, both in winters and summers. Nonetheless, the basic disposition of the basin to arrange itself in a dual pattern remains clear and indubitable, with ample variations of water levels having been observed across the years.

But in more recent years, the intense heat scorching the Lakes during the latest, extremely warm summers, and the increasing scarcity of rainfalls and snows, have endangered the very existence of these Apennine waters.

Pictures taken in 2007, 2011 and 2020 provide a gloomy vision of a progressive, though widely oscillating, decrease in the water content of the glacial basin: the two ponds appear to be fully parted, with an overall reduction of the liquid surfaces.

Fig. 95 - The Lakes of Pilate in August 2007

Fig. 96 - The Lakes of Pilate in November 2011

Fig. 97 - The Lakes of Pilate in May 2020

Conditions of strong depletion were not infrequent in the past, too. If we look at a picture dating to 1990, we find a similar contraction of the waters; and all this cannot but remind us of the sixteenth-century drawing which is found in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241, with the two ponds marked by a similar, substantial lack of waters.

Fig. 98 - The Lakes of Pilate in 1990

However, it is undeniable that complete depletion of the liquid content of both Lakes is increasingly becoming a sort of almost normal condition: the severe droughts which occurred in 2017 and 2020 rendered the two ponds a ghostly footprint of themselves, with the utter disappearance of all traces of water.

And the contrast between the large, single Lake as seen by Antoine de la Sale, and our current duplicated, dried-up Lakes is blatantly outright. And almost unbearable.

Before the above visions, we stand speechless.

Yet we must progress further into our investigations, and address the possible, additional reasons for the potential disappearance of the Lakes of Pilate.

Fig. 99 - The Lakes of Pilate thoroughly dried up in 2017

Fig. 100 - Vanished Lakes of Pilate in the summer of year 2020

19. Why are the Lakes fading away?

In recent years what was known in the past as the Lake of Pilate has shrunk to two small ponds, up to a point in which they both reduced to nothing.

Fig. 101 - The northernmost Lake of Pilate in September 2018

However, in the fifteenth century the Lake of the Sibyl was large and extended, though within the limited boundaries of the glacial valley set within the cliffs of Mount Vettore. And, across the subsequent centuries, the Lake seems to have maintained its health and shape (despite the natural, repeated, seasonal variations in the water content of the basin), as reported not only by the literary sources, but also by a number of cartographers: if the Lake had been substantially a duplicated pond, some of them would have known and drawn in their maps, basing on the reports provided to them by their local correspondents. The only instances of a dual-shaped pond, a typical summer condition, are presented in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and Father Fortunato Ciucci's *Chronicles of the Antique Town of*

Norsia, a sign that the duplication of the waters was not so frequent and was mainly caused by temporary summer droughts.

Certainly the second half of the nineteenth century was a turning point: from then on, the attestations to an increasing splitting of the basin dedicated to the name of Pontius Pilate are retrieved in many sources, both scholarly and cartographical. In the last quarter of the century a report written by Count Girolamo Orsi hints to a duplication of the waters. In 1879, the Lake was still seen as an ominous, single Lake by the members of the Italian Alpine Club; however, a few years later Giovanni Battista Miliani will describe the Lake as presenting itself in «the shape of spectacles», the same words which Pio Rajna, too, will use in 1897.

For the Lake of Pilate, the twentieth century is the age of increasing partition: across the annual seasons and the ceaseless variations of water levels, the basin will present a growing indentation duly represented in maps, aerial photographs and even vintage postcards. A notch that will eventually develop into a full separation of the two ponds, and total aridity in specific summer seasons of the current century.

Was such increasing depletion originated by some sort of collapse which happened, according to Pio Rajna, at the middle of the nineteenth century? We could not confirm Rajna's piece of information, provided to him by his local guides. Sure enough, a devastating earthquake hit Norcia and the adjoining land in 1859: however, we have no reports about severe damages which might have occurred in the area of Castelluccio di Norcia, not far from the Lake, nor we found any sources attesting to specific physical effects that might have been produced by the seismic waves on Mount Vettore and its glacial cirque, as it will actually happen one hundred fifty-seven years later during the frightful, much powerful 2016 earthquake.

May a possible reason be found in the most recent earthquakes? Scientists do not seem to support this sort of scenario.

In December 2019, a study on the potential variations of the hydrogeological conditions of the Lake after the 2016 seismic sequence, from which we already quoted at the beginning of the present research paper, highlighted «the absence of geomorphological evidence of seismic-induced surface fractures generated by the seismic sequence 2016-2017»:

thus, water was not missing as an effect of possible leaks caused by cracks opened in the Lake's bottom. The researchers concluded that «the complete drying of the lake, occurred in summer 2017, was probably due to meteorological reasons», rather than «not yet verified variations in the permeability characteristics of the surface deposits and/or bedrock affecting the infiltration towards the subsoil, caused by severe seismic shaking».

Fig. 102 - Analysis of the potential reasons for the depletion of the waters of the Lakes of Pilate (L. Martarelli et al., *The Pilato Lake (Sibillini Mts., Central Italy): first results of a study on the supposed variations of its hydrogeological conditions induced by the seismic sequence 2016-2017*, in *Acque sotterranee - Italian Journal of Groundwater*, Vol. 8, n. 4/158, 2019, p. 23 and 26)

According to the above study, if water was missing the phenomenon occurred out of «water overflow through the Fonte del Lago spring [towards the underlying valley, editor's note] [...], the evaporation from the lake surface [... and] the drainage through the scarcely permeable glacial deposits towards the Basal Calcareous Aquifer, hosted within the limestone at lower altitude», with no observable drainage effect from potential sinkholes produced in the rock by earthquakes.

Can depletion in the Lake's water have been induced by other sorts of physical effects? The answer is yes indeed.

In the present paper, we are about to set down the reasons for the potential, imminent disappearance of the Lakes of Pilate, in a looming future which is now close to us.

From the mid of the nineteenth century onwards, two nasty effects have been heavily affecting the health and shape of the former Lake of Pilate.

Let's start with the most critical, most severe factor that is leading Mount Vettore's basin in the direction of a slow, fated death.

And this is climate change.

20. Climate change: a golden, glacial period

It was in the fourteenth century that winters began to get cooler and snow invaded Europe: the continent was entering what scientists call the Little Ice Age (LIA). An age of lower temperatures which will last half a millennium.

There is no widespread agreement among researchers as to the characteristics, reasons and accurate dating of this weather phenomenon, which seems to have affected the Northern Hemisphere only. Its definition is the result of a number of studies involving many heterogeneous disciplines and sources, including history, literature, climatology, glaciology and even figurative arts. However, it is a fact that a series of clues appear to indicate that at some point in time Europe became colder, and that this moderate cooling lasted, with variations, until the mid of the nineteenth century.

The appearance of colder weather conditions over Europe was not distributed geographically in a homogeneous way. First reports of a specific cooling trend refer to Iceland and pack ice drifting around the northern-Atlantic isle (*Abrupt onset of the Little Ice Age triggered by volcanism and sustained by sea-ice/ocean feedbacks*, Miller et al., 2012):

«The expansion of ice caps after Medieval times was initiated by an abrupt and persistent snowline depression late in the 13th Century, and amplified in the mid 15th Century. [...] Sea ice was rarely present on the North Iceland shelf from 800 AD until the late 13th Century, when an abrupt rise in sea-ice proxies suggests a rapid increase in Arctic Ocean sea ice export,

followed by another increase around 1450 AD, after which sea ice was continuously present until the 20th Century. [...] LIA summer cold and ice growth began abruptly between 1275 and 1300 AD, followed by a substantial intensification 1430–1455 AD».

Fig. 103 - *The Frozen Thames, looking Eastwards towards Old London Bridge* (detail), a painting by Abraham Hondius, 1677 (Museum of London)

Further evidences of a European-wide cooling are provided by the occurrence of the Great Famine in the years 1315-1317, when unusual cold and heavy, persistent rains struck a large portion of Europe and caused an extensive failure of crops. The river Thames froze many times in the subsequent centuries, as attested by paintings as well. The winter season between 1709 and 1710 was known in Europe as "The Great Frost": it is considered as one of the coldest winters ever occurred in the Continent. And, throughout the LOI age, glaciers in the Alps seem to have gained in extension, as illustrated in a further research paper (*Glacier fluctuations during the past 2000 years*, Solomina et al., 2016):

«In the Alps the maximum extent of the glaciers was reached in the 17th - 19th centuries [...]. A maximum glacier advance also occurred in the Alps in the 14th century».

Another study (*The Little Ice Age signature in a 700-year high-resolution chironomid record of summer temperatures in the Central Eastern Alps*, Ilyashul et al., 2018) provides evidences of «a notable decreasing trend of -1.2 °C from ca AD 1300 until ca AD 1800 [...] with] a prolonged period of predominantly cooler conditions during AD 1530–1920, which is temporally largely equivalent to the climatically defined LIA in Europe. [...] The main LIA phase appears to have consisted of two cold time intervals divided by slightly warmer episodes in the second half of the 1600s. The most severe cooling occurred during the eighteenth century».

Fig. 104 - Estimated temperature variations from year 1000 AD to year 2000 AD (*Third Assessment Report on Climate Change*, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2001), p. 3

Bits and pieces of information, which scientists are trying to match with the available data on average estimated temperatures, with an eye to the subsequent period of dramatic warming due to the Industrial Revolution and contemporary human activity, as shown in the diagram included in the *Third Assessment Report on Climate Change* (2001) elaborated by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: a decreasing line from the

Middle Ages to 1850, the footprint of the Little Ice Age, and then a fast rise towards today's global warming temperature levels.

So, in past centuries the weather in Europe was cooler. Hubert Lamb, a passionate, early forerunner of the investigation into past climate variations, in his book *Climate, History and the Modern World* (1982) wrote that «snowfall was much heavier than recorded before or since, and the snow lay on the ground for many months longer than it does today». It can be assumed that snowfalls were more abundant and accumulated snow persisted on mountaintops for longer times.

What happened in Italy? What happened to our Lake of Pilate during the Little Ice Age?

Fig. 105 - *Frozen Lagoon*, a painting by Battaglioli, Francesco, 1788 (Museo del Settecento veneziano, Ca' Rezzonico, Venice)

A number of sources and reports are related to specific events occurred in the Italian peninsula across many centuries. As an example, an insight

paper (*The Little Ice Age in Italy from documentary proxies and early instrumental records*, Camuffo et al., 2014) highlights the years in which the Lagoon of Venice froze totally or partially: extremely cold winters occurred in 1408, 1413, 1477, 1511, 1560, 1684, 1776, 1820 and 1864, with a number of less severe episodes interspersed amid the listed dates, with only a handful of occurrences being registered during the twentieth century.

So, while glaciers in the Alps extended, the prolonged effects of cooling also acted on the southern portion of Europe, including Italy, as inferred by another scholar (*The 'Little Ice Age' and its Geomorphological Consequences in Mediterranean Europe*, Grove, 2001):

«Alpine glacier advances in the 'Little Ice Age' took place in the decades around 1320, 1600, 1700 and 1810. They were the outcome of snowier winters and cooler summers than those of the twentieth century. Documentary records from Crete in particular, and also from Italy, southern France and southeast Spain point to a greater frequency in Mediterranean Europe's mountainous regions of severe floods, droughts and frosts at times of 'Little Ice Age' Alpine glacier advances. Deluges, when more than 200 mm of rain fall within 24 hours, are most frequent on mountainous areas near the coast».

Therefore, the climate in Italy between the fourteenth century and the mid of the nineteenth century was certainly cooler, and more snow and rain used to fall on the whole peninsula. Including mountainous reliefs.

Has all this any relevance to the issue which concerns the shape of the Lake of Pilate, in the Sibillini Mountain Range, at the center of Italy?

Yes indeed. This is actually the sort of climate-related finding we expected to register. Because the epoch of the Little Ice Age is actually the very same multicentennial period during which the Lake of Pilate has been presenting itself as a single, gloomy, ominous basin.

A Lake effectively fed by rainfalls and snowfalls. And made healthy by generous accumulations of snow deposited over the steep versants of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque.

A single Lake, as it was described by the literary sources dating back to the fourteenth century (Petrus Berchorius) and the fifteenth (Antoine de la Sale), and then across the subsequent centuries in written references and geographical maps. Always a single basin of dark waters, apart from the specific mentions provided by manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241 and Father Fortunato Ciucci, which both portray a dual-shaped Lake observed during the summer season.

The Little Ice Age, a European-wide climate-related phenomenon marked by lower temperatures and a general though moderate cooling of the whole continent, is possibly the main reason for the semblance of the Lake of Pilate across many centuries, and up to the second half of the nineteenth century.

At that time, something began to change.

As we comprehensively illustrated in the previous paragraphs of the present research paper, the Lake of Pilate was gradually turning into two separate Lakes: the Lakes of Pilate as we know them today.

And one of the main drivers for the transformation of our necromantic basin is always the same: climate change.

Or, more appropriately, man-driven climate change.

21. Climate change: is the Lake's end near?

At the end of the nineteenth century, Vittorio Sella, the great alpinist and photographer, whose uncle was Quintino Sella, the founder of the Italian Alpine Club, ascended a number of elevated peaks of the Alps to portray the gorgeous, panoramic vistas with his camera equipped with large, high-quality photographic plates.

At the time, he did not know; yet he was dramatically contributing to the advancement of contemporary climatology, by providing future scientists with invaluable evidences of a most critical environmental process.

This process was climate change.

His pictures of alpine glaciers are being presently used by modern photographers and researchers to assess the fast-paced retreat of the ice masses under the pressure of global warming. Fabiano Ventura's project *On the trail of the glaciers* is currently documenting, with stunning photographs taken from the same positions as Vittorio Sella's, the shrinking of the glaciers which lie amid the Italian Alps: the decrease in snowfalls and the ever-growing heat which floods the icy surfaces during the warmest summers in the last one hundred fifty years are speeding up a melting process that was possibly triggered centuries ago by the start of the Industrial Revolution, in Europe initially and then throughout the whole world.

Fig. 106 - A comparison between a shot taken by Vittorio Sella in 1894 and a contemporary image captured by Fabiano Ventura of the Money Glacier on the Grand Paradis Range in the Alps which separate Italy and France

Fig. 107 - Another comparison between a photograph taken in 1900 and a contemporary shot of the Morteratsch Glacier on the Bernina Range set between Italy and Switzerland

Similar studies are being conducted in other portions of the Alps: in Switzerland, other astounding pictures provide a sad vision of the doom that is looming over all alpine glaciers, with a dramatic retreat of the ice and a depletion of the stocks of frozen water.

On a general, worldwide basis the fate of glaciers is gloomily outlined in the *Fifth Assessment Report on Climate Change* (2013) edited by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change:

«More than 600 glaciers have disappeared over the past decades. Even if there is no further warming, many more glaciers will disappear. It is also likely that some mountain ranges will lose most, if not all, of their glaciers. [...] Larger glaciers will continue to shrink over the next few decades, even if temperatures stabilise. Smaller glaciers will also continue to shrink, but they will adjust their extent faster and many will ultimately disappear entirely».

This is the incoming death of glaciers. A termination which certainly is strongly linked with the condition of our Lakes set in the Apennines, between the provinces of Umbria and Marche.

Because climate change, of course, is not limited to Alps.

A remarkable paper issued by the Regional Administration for Environment and Preservation of Emilia-Romagna in 2010 (*Climatology and annual variations of snow on the Apennine in Emilia-Romagna*, De Bellis et al.) analyses the trends in snowfalls and accumulated snow in a mountainous region which lies not far from the Sibillini Mountain Range, on their northwestern side. According to the study, the climatology of snow in the southern portion of the investigated area, the Romagna, is similar to that «of the Adriatic versant of Central Apennines», which means the Sibillini region.

The diagrams processed by the researchers on the amount of snowfalls in the area in the second half of the twentieth century are highly significant. The thickness of the accumulated snow in winters, as measured by a number of stations set across the Emilia-Romagna Apennines, shows a dramatic decrease in the deposited quantities of snow at the end of the

1980s. This is linked to a steady growth of the maximum temperatures in winters on those same mountainous reliefs across the years.

In the research paper, an interesting correlation is established with a global index specifically used in contemporary climatology: the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO).

The NAO is a large-scale atmospheric phenomenon which affects climate variations across the European and northern-Atlantic regions. It is connected to the positions and seasonal parameters of the Azores High and Icelandic Low, with a strong influence on jet streams at tropospheric altitude. According to the study, the strong decrease in snowfalls observed in the Romagna region in the 1980s «is matched by the very same period in which the NAO index begins to grow».

Fig. 108 - Trends in accumulated snow levels in winters in the Apennine portion of the Italian region of Emilia-Romagna between 1950 and 2000 (in *Climatology and annual variations of snow on the Apennine in Emilia-Romagna*, De Bellis et al., Regional Administration for Environment and Preservation of Emilia Romagna, 2010), p. 60

So the NAO index appears to be a main factor in the triggering of snowfalls and snow accumulation over the land of Emilia-Romagna and the nearby Apennines; and its influence extends across the whole European territory, as shown by a Swiss study and a further Romanian research carried out respectively on the Alps and the Carpathian Mountains, which both led to a same conclusion.

Vanishing glaciers, decrease in rainfalls and snowfalls, ominous variations of the North Atlantic Oscillation: all these factors, all linked to the current change which is affecting global weather and climate, are marking the potential, impending end of the Lakes of Pilate.

And we want to conclude this sorrowful paragraph by providing a true, unmistakable vision of the main factor which will lead the Lakes of Mount Vettore to their final death.

In the previous paragraph, dedicated to the 'Little Ice Age', we already saw a diagram taken from the IPCC's *Third Assessment Report on Climate Change* (2001), showing, on its rightmost portion, the rapid, amazing, almost unbelievable rise in global temperature observed from the middle of the nineteenth century and up to our current days.

A further, astounding, updated view is provided by a diagram presented in the *Climate Change 2014 Report* issued by the IPCC.

It's a diagram which shows the global average temperatures between 1850 and 2012.

Fig. 109 - Globally averaged combined land and ocean surface temperature anomaly from 1850 to 2000 (in *Climate Change 2014 - Synthesis Report*, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014), p. 3

It rises. And rises. And rises. Very fast.

And another diagram is shown in the same report.

It's our world. The Earth. And it is warming up. Quickly.

Increased heat. Vanishing glaciers. Less snow. Less rain. In this gloomy framework, there is no question about the final destiny of the Lakes of Pilate, in the Sibillini Mountain Range.

They will disappear. Their cradle of rock will remain eventually empty.

Fig. 110 - Observed change in surface temperature 1901 - 2012 (in *Climate Change 2014 - Synthesis Report*, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014), p. 41

And this will not be a problem only for a small, legendary, fascinating basin of water lost amid the Mountains of the Sibyl.

This will be a problem for mankind as a whole.

22. Landslides: when the mountain swallows its siblings

Climate change is certainly leading the Lakes of Pilate, once a single, impressive Lake, towards extinction. An extinction which is basically to be considered as a side effect of a much larger, global-scale process that is

putting at risk huge geographical features all around the world, including glaciers in the Alps.

However, we strongly repute that possibly this is not the one and only effect, of a nasty nature, which has been unfavourably affecting the life of the Lake of Pilate across the last one hundred fifty years.

Another physical effect, on a local scale, may have significantly influenced the shape of the water basin set amid the cliffs of Mount Vettore. An additional effect which, when combined with the decrease in snowfalls and rainfalls due to climate change, is equivalent to a mortal blow inflicted to our legendary Lake: a stifling grip around its neck, leading to utter suffocation.

And this grip is landslides.

As we already noted in a previous paragraph, the whole area of the Sibillini Mountain Range is subject to recurrent earthquakes and violent seasonal storms. And Mount Vettore's glacial cirque is at the core of all this.

Fig. 111 - The bottom covered with rocky debris of the glacial valley in which the Lakes of Pilate lie

The very shape and nature of the rocky cradle that once housed a glacier render the site prone to landslides from the overhanging cliffs which encircle the whole arched space. The rock is fractured and grinded by the

action of the now-vanished ice mass. Debris and rubble cover the bottom of the cirque. Earthquakes and storms continue to effect an uninterrupted strain on the titanic walls of sheer stone, from which pebbles and rocks and boulders, across the decades and centuries, keep on sliding and falling onto the Lake.

This ceaseless process has induced a progressive raise in the elevation of the Lake's bottom, thus leaving less volume available to the water content of the basin, and creating a growing barrier of debris at the middle of the glacial cirque, which eventually caused the partition of the Lake, in earlier times a single basin, into two ordinarily separated ponds.

So, in the past the glacial cirque was markedly deeper, allowing for more water; across the centuries, the site's bottom slowly raised, and less water can be accommodated within the cirque without overflowing from the northern side into the underlying valley. Gilberto Pambianchi, a geologist at the University of Camerino, claimed that the process was accelerated by the great seismic sequence which occurred in 2016: according to his estimate, the landslides which followed the earthquakes precipitated stones and debris right into the Lakes, with a rise of the bottom's elevation of about three feet, though this figure has not yet been confirmed nor reported in scientific papers.

Fig. 112 - The landslide on the western side of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque

However, we are interested in less recent landslides. Are there any of them which are visible around the glacial cirque that houses the Lakes of Pilate?

Yes. Ancient, historical landslides are there.

A first one is found on the western side of the rounded glacial valley: a funnel-shaped mass of debris coming down from a vertex set up above, below the peaks of Cima del Redentore and Pizzo del Diavolo. This large quantity of rubble keeps on rolling and falling into the smaller, southernmost pond, which appears to be almost overwhelmed by the never-ending accumulation of stones.

But it is the second landslide that possibly sealed the destiny of the larger Lake of Pilate as it was known in the past.

This further landslide is set on the opposite, eastern side of the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore. And it is impressive altogether.

Fig. 113 - The landslide on the eastern side of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque

It originates from the mountainside which goes up to the most elevated peak of the whole mount, once called the Petrara peak. A sort of wound, a veritable scar marks this portion of the cliff: from it, as if it were a spring of

fresh mountain water, rocks and debris seem to pour out and sprinkle onto the underlying Lakes.

Such copious flow of stones and pebbles is hurled right onto the low ridge that separates the two ponds. Actually, it makes up and feeds that ridge.

This is the landslide that gave rise to the two Lakes: from a single Lake to a dual configuration, increasingly parted by an ever-growing mass of rocks ceaselessly falling into the waters from the eastern side of the glacial cirque.

It is manifestly clear that centuries and centuries of slowly-flowing landslides, fuelled and accelerated on specific occasions by earthquakes, storms and temperature variations, gradually filled up the bottom of the Lake's basin. A simultaneous, claw-shaped flank attack conducted on both sides, the eastern and the western, of the original Lake.

In the long term, a deadly attack.

When the bottom of the basin will be filled with enough rubble so as to reach the elevation of the front dike to the northern side of the basin (6,463 feet, as reported in a previous chapter in this same research paper), the Lake or Lakes will not be able to form anymore: water will just leave the glacial cirque unhindered by flowing straight down into the valley underneath.

Across the centuries, the Lake's bottom has raised and raised up to the present level (6365 feet): still a gap of some 100 feet needs to be filled before the waters reach the northern dike's level. The landslides have still much work to do to achieve the utter eradication of the Lakes of Pilate. Mount Vettore is quietly, relentlessly swallowing up its own siblings, nested between its rocky arms.

And yet the landslides are working nicely and steadily, with sudden accelerations due to earthquakes. They already succeeded in parting the Lake into two smaller Lakes, by building up a sort of ridge between the northern and southern basins.

Did this loading process experience some sort of boost at the middle of the nineteenth century? We actually don't know, because a geological investigation is needed if we intend to ascertain the age of the most significant flows of rubbles which are present within the two landslides. As a matter of fact, it was in 1879 that the aristocratic members of the Italian Alpine Clube saw the Lake in its healthy, single form for the last time; and it was in 1897, at the end of the nineteenth century, that Pio Rajna beheld the two Lakes fully separated by a portion of dry land, even though accumulated snow was all around: a sign that the central ridge was becoming high enough to ensure a successful partition of the two Lakes despite snowfalls and rainfalls.

Fig. 114 - The Lakes of Pilate threatened by landslides and global warming

A deadly attack, as we stated earlier in this chapter. But the more deadly it appears to be, when we come to consider the concurrent action of climate change and global warming. Less snow. Less rain. Less space available to accommodate water. A relentless process, which is going ahead and ahead.

Until the Lakes of Pilate will eventually die.

23. The legend lives on

Pontius Pilate and the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the Italian Apennines. A necromantic Lake entitled to the first-century Roman prefect who sentenced Jesus Christ to death. A basin of dark waters encircled by the precipitous ravines of Mount Vettore: a sinister, solitary nest that once housed a glacier set in the Sibillini Mountain Range, and vanished thousands of years ago.

Fig. 115 - The Lake of Pilate as portrayed in a miniature contained in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 1r)

In the present research paper, we have been riding through the centuries, in search of the shape of the Lake of Pilate: one Lake, two Lakes, and, finally, no Lake at all.

A long journey that has taken us from the sinister Lake of past centuries down to the scant, depleted Lakes of our present times, and their anticipated, imminent death in a future that is as close as global climate change.

We started our travel from the fourteenth century, with Petrus Berchorius and his emotional words: «amid the peaks which raise near that town [Norcia] there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them...». Then, we joined French gentleman Antoine de la Sale in his 1420 visit to the Lake, named after Pilate and the Sibyl. From then on, descriptions and references of an ominous Lake sitting amid the mountains of the Sibyl, in central Italy, begin to follow one after another, across the fifteenth, sixteenth and seventeenth century.

Pope Pius II Piccolomini, Flavio Biondo, Arnold von Harff, Leandro Alberti provide mentions about the gloomy Lake set amid the cragged cliffs of the mountains of the Sibyl. A single, ominous Lake, as portrayed in many geographical maps across the centuries: its likeness is depicted on the walls of the illustrious Gallery of Maps at the Vatican Museums in Rome; Giuseppe Moleti, in his edition of Ptolemy's *Geography* draws a single Lake, and an elongated version of it is presented by Gerard de Jode in his *Speculum Orbis Terrae*; it pops up from the map set down by Giubilio and Maggi in 1592, then it appears in Gerardus Mercator's *Atlas sive Cosmographicae Meditationes de fabrica mundi et fabricati figura*, in Giovanni Antonio Magini's *Italy - A General Description*, in Philipp Clüver's *Italia Antiqua*, and in Joan Blaeu's *Nova et accuratissima totius terrarum orbis tabula*.

In all the listed literary and cartographic references, the Lake of Pilate is always one: a single, impressive Lake, concealed beneath the rocky arms of Mount Vettore. Only one instance, in the sixteenth century, provides us with a different vision: two scanty, separate Lakes, as attested in manuscript Vat. Lat. 5241, a graphical account of a visit possibly carried out during a hot, dry summer. But this account remained buried for centuries, hidden amid the many vellum folia which contained a collection

of ancient Latin inscription, and was found and taken back to light only in 1982.

So, in past centuries, the usual shape of the Lake of Pilate was that of one basin, with temporary summer depletions which led to a partition marked by two smaller Lakes. Nonetheless, its fame across Europe concerned a single Lake: it was one, and it was necromantic, and it was legendary.

When we reached the seventeenth and eighteenth century, we found nothing different from the past: the Lake was still represented as a single Lake, consistently firm in its uniqueness, as we retrieve it in further maps edited by Silvestro Amanzio Moroncelli and Guillaume de L'Isle. We also retraced the steps of two great Jesuit cartographers, Christopher Maire and Ruggero Giuseppe Boscovich, with their misadventurous passage across the Sibillini Mountain Range: they did not see the Lake of Pilate, so that the basin is utterly missing in their comprehensive map of the Papal States. And we found another, isolated description of the Lakes in their depleted summer form: it is contained in the *Chronicles of the Antique Town of Norsia* by Father Fortunato Ciucci, who wrote that they appeared «in the form of spectacles», adding that «I saw from various signs that they come together making up a single lake; but in Summer, in the lack of running water, they split, so that they are seen in the shape of eyeglasses». But his text had no circulation at all: only four manuscripted copies of the *Chronicles* are extant, and they were never printed in a book, if not in a modern edition dating to 2003.

It is in the course of the nineteenth century that a change begins to be apparent, amid the Sibillini Mountain Range. However, no modification is still visible when a geographer of the Imperial and Royal Military Geographical Institute of Austria draws a gorgeous maps of Tuscany and the Papal States: between 1841 and 1843, the Lake is still seen by the professional eyes of Giovanni Marieni as a single basin, and so reported in the relevant cartographic sheet.

The second half of the century brings in a new shape for the Lake. Initially, nothing seems to have undergone any change: in the summer season, the Lake appears split in two smaller ponds as it occurred in past centuries, too. We can read about its shape in the report written during the summer of 1877 by Count Girolamo Orsi, an illustrious member of the then-young

Italian Alpine Club: «between the two branches [of Mount Vettore], at the very bottom of titanic ravines, the Lakes of Pilate are found», he writes, «the Lakes of Pilate, and their deep-blue waters, and the frightful ravine nearby». And, in 1887, Giovanni Battista Miliani also sees the two summer Lakes: «down in the valley on the left side, the Lake of Pilate is seen; in summer, as when I saw it, it has a shape of spectacles».

And there are also occasions in which the Lake still retains its original, impressive appearance as a single mirror of waters. When the members of the Italian Alpine Club visited Mount Vettore in 1879, they beheld the ancient vista already described by Antoine de la Sale more than four hundred years earlier: a large, single Lake, ominously nested within the arched crests of the mountain, the way it appears in the drawing published by *L'Illustrazione Italiana* at the time. A vision also confirmed by another report, independently written by Countess Lucia Rossi Scotti, who had joined the alpinists on their climb that day: «... the greenish, gloomy Lake of Pilate, lying in that gorge out of the melting of snows...».

But at the end of the nineteenth century time has come for the Lake to undergo a change. For unknown reasons, snows and rains appear not to be able to fill it up to its single-basin shape anymore. From now on the Lake of Pilate will increasingly begin to turn into the two Lakes of Pilate we know today.

The most accurate description of the new typical shape of our legendary basin is set down by Italian philologist Pio Rajna in 1897: «the Lake appeared to me divided in two elliptical mirrors [...]. The comparison with a pair of spectacles [...] is truly pictorial». An usual occurrence, in summer. But that specific summer plenty of snow was there, accumulated on the sides of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque, manifestly without being able to confer the Lake its larger, single shape:

«I found snow in fair quantity around the lake; and normally Mount Vettore never denies this garniture to itself, as Antonio told me. In Foce (a small hamlet lying in the valley underneath) people told me that once there was a period of nine years when a lack of snowfalls was registered in winters, too, but this occurred and ended twenty years ago».

Had anything happened to the Lake of Pilate? According to Rajna, «today the lake is not what it was in past times anymore»: some forty years earlier «it broke the natural dike at its front, a barrier that never formed again. So Antoine de la Sale beheld a lake with a significantly different appearance, and deeper». And, truly enough, in 1859 a great earthquake struck the territory of Norcia: was it the cause for a dramatic collapse of the northern side of the glacial basin which holds the necromantic Lake? Did the seismic waves change the appearance of the basin forever, with an inability to return to its single form even when snow was present?

As we detailed in the present research paper, we cannot tell. The 1859 earthquake was certainly strong enough to turn Norcia into a heap of ruins; yet, its magnitude and epicentre do not seem to feature the attributes and power required to affect Mount Vettore in so dramatic a way, and no reports on such conjectural event have ever been found in local records as yet. Furthermore, if such an event had actually happened, the members of the Italian Alpine Club could not have experienced a vision of a single Lake as late as 1879, as reported by an Italian magazine of the time.

Anyway, despite its final, occasional appearance as a single basin, starting from the second half of the nineteenth century the shape of the Lake of Pilate was destined to tread a path of growing duplication, and increasing water depletion: the Lake will begin to present itself as a basin substantially split in two smaller ponds, either utterly parted or joined by a narrow strip of water. In summers and winters. Because, during winters, it usually will not regain its original, single form. A sign of growing scarcity of snowfalls and rainfalls, and possibly of variations in the physical configuration of the rocky basin.

The late nineteenth-century cartography drawn by the Italian Military Geographical Institute shows an elongated Lake now visibly indented at the middle, ready to part in two fully distinct ponds. The same deep notch will be portrayed by Cesare Lippi-Boncambi in his drawing dating to 1947. And though other military maps edited in 1952 present the Lake in its flourishing though elongated form, actual reality at that time was markedly different: vintage postcards and aerial photographs cannot but ascertain that the Lake of Pilate had already changed its shape into two smaller ponds, increasingly affected by a significant lack of water supply and possibly

overwhelmed by remarkable masses of debris ceaselessly falling from the adjacent crests.

Partition, depletion and insufficient provision of water. A condition that will be repeatedly observed across the first decades of the twenty-first century. The pictures of the Lakes, sadly shrunk to two tiny ponds, and the portraits of a glacial valley utterly deprived of any trace of water, as happened in 2017 and 2020, are truly heartbreaking.

In the present paper, we summarized the potential reasons which may be at the origin of such severe depletion. We could not confirm Pio Rajna's piece of information concerning a mid-nineteenth-century collapse of the Lake's front dike. We reviewed the position of researchers as to the possible drainage of waters from the bottom of the basin into the underlying bedrock, owing to new cracks and fissures potentially produced in the soil by the 2016 earthquakes; but accurate surveys have shown no evidence of such a drainage at the site.

So we identified two main effects, both of a nasty nature, which are affecting the health conditions and overall shape of the Lakes of Pilate. Two adverse effects that are gradually bringing the mountain basin to a fated, inexorable termination.

A first, most critical cause for the increasing depletion of the Lakes of Pilate is climate change. And this statement, alone, resounds in our ears as a sentence of death.

From the fourteenth century to the middle of the nineteenth, the Little Ice Age, a climate condition which affected Europe and was marked by moderately lower temperatures as compared to the previous time periods, ensured an optimal water feeding to the Lake of Pilate: winters were colder, snowfalls were abundant, plenty of accumulated snow was present on the Sibillini Mountain Range, and copious rainfalls helped the Lake to preserve its water balance.

Thus, throughout many centuries, and as attested by the many sources we explored in the present research paper, the Lake of Pilate was a well-fed, single, impressive, necromantic mountain basin. With only temporary depletion affecting the shape of the Lake during the good season.

Then climate began to change.

The effects of man-driven changes started to manifest from the mid of the nineteenth century onwards, with a rapid rise of temperatures around the globe. And the Italian Apennines, like the whole of Europe, were affected, too.

The Lake of Pilate began to mutate: the transformation process into two separate Lakes was gradual, as snowfalls became increasingly less intense on average, and the same happened to rainfalls.

In August 1876, Count Girolamo Orsi was able to behold, in the glacial cirque within Mount Vettore, «the Lakes of Pilate [...], fed by an extended volume of ice, the seed of a persistent glacier, which hides itself down there from direct sunlight. [...] The perennial snows down there, [...] in the gorge set northeast of the peak of Petrarà; the same snows that feed those Lakes...» (in the original Italian text: «i Laghi di Pilato, alimentati da quella estesa lente di ghiaccio, embrione di un ghiacciaio perenne, che laggiù si nasconde ai raggi del sole. [...] Quelle nevi perpetue interposte ai tre culmini, là in quella gola nord-est del Petrarà, che danno alimento a quei, laghi»).

And Giovanni Battista Miliani, in 1886, wrote that «across all the valley [where the Lakes of Pilate lie], in the spots most sheltered from direct sunrays, accumulated snow persists, which only seldom melts and vanishes in summers» (in the original Italian text: «In tutta questa valle, nei luoghi più riparati dal sole, esistono depositi di neve, che assai di rado sgelano completamente in estate»).

Today, those perennial snows exist no more, thoroughly erased by the scorching action of the summer heat generated by global warming: the very same warming that is killing glaciers all over the world.

A process which began to be noticeable at the end of the nineteenth century, as reported by Pio Rajna in his writings:

«I found snow in fair quantity around the lake; and normally Mount Vettore never denies this garniture to itself, as Antonio told me. In Foce [a small

hamlet lying in the valley underneath] people told me that once there was a period of nine years when there a lack of snowfalls was registered in winters, too, but this occurred and ended twenty years ago».

[In the original Italian text: «Ho trovato neve in discreta quantità dattorno al lago: e per solito il Vettore non si priva mai, come dice Antonio, di questo ornamento. A Foce mi si è detto tuttavia esserci stato un periodo di nove anni, finito da un ventennio, in cui neve non s'ebbe neppure in inverno»].

So the Lake indented and then parted, two distinct Lakes appeared, and not only in dry summers but all year long, and all years. And, as global warming grew, snow and rain became unable to sustain the basin's needs in terms of water, with scant supplies and periods of severe droughts.

The result of this grievous process is emptiness and dryness.

However, this is not the only effect which is leading the Lakes of Pilate to an irrevocable death. Because a second, most severe cause is landslides.

Like deadly claws, two major historical landslides loom over the Lakes of Pilate from the western and eastern sides of Mount Vettore's glacial cirque. For centuries and centuries they have been sending rocks and rubble and debris from the high cliffs straight into the waters underneath. And the eastern landslide, in particular, has gradually built up a central ridge, which splits the original Lake in two different ponds.

So the bottom of the basins is raising and raising, across many centuries and the multiple earthquakes that certainly provide a contribution to the acceleration of the long, historical, uninterrupted process of filling-up. A process that, possibly, experienced some sort of advancement between 1879 and 1897: from the vision of a healthy Lake as seen by the Italian alpinists to the parted, fully-separate Lakes observed by Pio Rajna, despite the presence of melting snow.

Landslides and bottom raising. Climate change and water depletion. Nasty effects which suffocate and choke the basin set amid the cliffs of Mount Vettore.

That's why we are now facing the impending, final, irrevocable death of the Lakes of Pilate.

At all appearances, the Lake of Pilate of past centuries, in its illustrious, single shape as it was celebrated for many hundreds of years across Europe, is extant nomore. And it will never come back.

And the Lake as we ourselves know it today, in its lesser form made up by two smaller, separate Lakes, is currently dying.

Here they are, in a beautiful satellite picture taken in July, 2017. They are small and powerless and vulnerable. They are only a pale ghost of what the Lake used to be in past centuries. And they are fading away.

Fig. 116 - The Lakes of Pilate

Yet their pure, utterly clear waters are still shimmering with billions of sparks of light. Their history seems to shine through their present fragility. Their legend - its legend, of a Lake concealed within the remote peaks of the Apennines, in central Italy, has been talking to people for centuries across all nations of Europe. Its mystery still resounds, in our present days,

in our fascinated ears, when we still read the ancient, blood-curdling tales of the necromantic waters which house demons and raise tempests, as we strive to bring to light the enigma which lies under its liquid, crystal-like surface, the way we did in a previous, groundbreaking research paper (*Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend*).

Fig. 117 - The Lakes of Pilate shimmering with light

And we want to see it, the Lake, for a last time, the way it was in the ripeness of the early centuries during which visitors flocked by its shore and mentions flowed through manuscripts and printed books.

Here is the Lake of Pilate, as Antoine de la Sale saw it, six hundred years ago. A sinister, single, impressive Lake, fully deserving its dedication to a key figure of the Gospels, Pontius Pilate. A Lake of mystery. A Lake of dream.

The Lake of Pilate may be dying. But its legendary fascination will live on forever.

Fig. 118 - An artist's impression of the Lake of Pilate as it was centuries ago

Michele Sanvico